

**Seasonal movement & activity
of Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows
in West Greenland
as determined by satellite**

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By

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*Raw data available at Greenland Institute of Natural Resources:
F:/40-59/PaFu/42/Landpattedyr/ 35 ALCOA Rensdyrspring

Summary (English)

In May 2008 GPS satellite collars were deployed on 40 cows from the Akia-Maniitsoq (AM) caribou (*Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus*) population. In the period 2008-2010, the satellite-collared cows provided locations, which we analysed for movements, spatial distribution, calving sites, location attributes, seasonal activity periods, and habitat resource selection. The AM caribou are substantially less documented than herds in North America. The results in this report are particularly valuable for management in Greenland because they establish a baseline for AM habitat use in the current absence of significant development and infrastructure in the Central region. However, the short study period and small sample size, exacerbated by high mortality, weaken results. Although obtaining collar data in Greenland is difficult and costly, a longer time series with a stable large number of collared caribou is necessary before sweeping conclusions can be supported.

AM cows behave similarly to the mountain ecotype of caribou rather than the barren-ground. Calving was not confined to specific exclusive calving grounds close to the Ice Cap. Birthing cows spaced-away in a continuum across the entire Central region, from seacoast to Ice Cap. There is little relevance to protecting specific exclusive calving grounds in the AM region. Instead, conservation measures would profit from applying a broad-scale habitat management approach to the widespread AM calving habitat. Elevation was a good predictor for probability of cow occurrence at calving. Whether in a xeric zone or not, south facing slopes around 600 m elevation with snow were favoured. Although timing and width of the emergent vegetation period and possibly rain avoidance may be the driving factors behind choice of high elevation for calving by parturient AM cows, these remain to be investigated. AM calving appears to begin earlier than previously assumed, and suggests that the period for protection measures might be shifted forward. Habitat possessing the preferred attributes for birthing comprises 42-45% of the Central region. Thus although calving range is essential for caribou production, at present it is not likely limiting the AM population. However, given the high fidelity by AM cows to previous birthing sites, a warming Arctic or anthropogenic influences could have negative impacts if cows are displaced to habitats less favourable for calf survival.

Mortality among satellite-collared cows was high and much appeared due to harvest. If common to the entire population, this would have played a major role in the decline of AM abundance from 2001 to 2010.

Patterns of annual movement confirmed a southwest-northeast axis. Distance moved could be short, with individuals typically at the western end of their axis in winter and eastern end in summer. Each cow utilized just a fraction of the available area. This strongly indicates population sub-division within the Central region and suggests that the entire AM population will not be influenced when either stochastic weather events or management actions affect only a portion of the region.

Patterns of seasonal movement revealed 10 seasonal activity periods, which were associated with specific habitat attributes. Elevation was the primary habitat

attribute that varied significantly across the seasonal activity periods. Breeding occurred at low elevations. If hunting seasons coincide with the rut, then human disturbance may negatively influence breeding and subsequently calf production. Caribou vulnerability to harvest would also likely increase because of their relative accessibility to hunters.

Daily movement patterns varied throughout the year. Cows moved least in early March making it optimal for aerial survey. July had maximum movement, suggesting insect harassment as the cause and supporting the necessity of insect relief habitat. During the calving period, a characteristic daily movement pattern was assumed to indicate a birthing event, i.e., rise from normal immediately preceding a sharp drop to near zero and thereafter a gradual rise. In future, birthing could be validated by visually locating satellite-collared cows by airplane or helicopter, or equipping the satellite-collars with video capability.

Habitat attributes are not evenly distributed. Relative to the entire Central region, and in contrast to calving habitat, the available area is small for late summer, fall and winter habitats. These could be limiting for the AM population. Specifically, the largest tract of winter habitat, *Akia*, albeit still small in size, is vulnerable to south westerly storm systems that can render winter forage unavailable or energetically costly to access. Thus, special attention and protection through fine-scale habitat management may be appropriate. AM caribou abundance would likely benefit if for those habitats that are scarce, a) caribou access was preserved, b) anthropogenic disturbance was mitigated, and c) that densities of AM caribou were kept below carrying capacity of these limited ranges.

Management is best tailor-made to the population, the seasonal activity under consideration and the amount of habitat available for that activity. Conservation efforts should address not just one several seasonal ranges vital to reproduction, insect relief and survival. Protecting parturient cows and their birthing habitat is not a one-shot cure for ensuring recovery or sustainability of caribou populations.

Caribou roam. Globally, caribou range shifts are common, even for 'sacrosanct' calving areas. Thus, management must consider conserving currently unused areas for potential future use by caribou. Meanwhile, human influences on the landscape are recognized factors that can exacerbate caribou declines. In North America, the current threshold proposed for preventing caribou decline, is that 65% of the total range remains unexposed to human disturbance. Proactive management and conservation directed towards preserving large undisturbed intact landscapes, relevant for several seasonal activities and their movement corridors, would foster caribou conservation now and for future generations.

Eqikkaaneq (Greenlandic)

Piniarfimmi Akia-Maniitsumi (AM) kulavannik (*Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus*) 40-nik qaammataasamut nassitsissutitalinnik 2008-mi maajip qaammataani qungasequtsersuisoqarpoq. Tuttut qungasequserneqarsimasut ukiuni 2008-2010 malittarineqarput; nuttartarnerat, siammarsimassusaat, norrisarfii, sumiiffinni ataasiakkaani uumaniarnerminni atugaat, ukiup kaajallakkiartortarnerani uumaniarnerminni atugaat uumaniarfissaminnillu neriniarfissaminnik toqqaasarnerat misissoqqissaarneqarput. Akia-Maniitsup tuttui Amerika avannarliup tamarmiusup tuttoqatigiiaavisulli misissugarineqarsimatiginngillat. Taamaattumik nalunaarusiaq manna Kalaallit Nunaanni aqutsinermut pingaaruteqarluinnartutut tunngavissaqqissutullu oqaatigisariaqarpoq, Akia-Maniitsup nunataata inunnit aammalu soorlu inuit sanaartornerannit suli sunniivigineqarpallaarsimannginnerata nalaani tuttut nunamik qanoq atuinerannik takussutissiisuummat.

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Resume (Danish)

I maj 2008 blev 40 simler i rensdyrbestanden (*Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus*) i Akia-Maniitsoq-området udstyret med halsbånd med satellitsendere. Senderne viste i perioden 2008-2010 simlernes placering, som blev analyseret mht. bevægelse, rumlig udbredelse, kælvningsområder, lokale forhold, årstidsvariationer i aktivitet og valg af habitat. Akia-Maniitsoq-renskyrene er ikke nær så velundersøgt som bestandene i Nordamerika. Denne rapport er specielt værdifuld for forvaltning i

Grønland, fordi den danner en *baseline* – dvs. et referencepunkt – for Akia-Maniitsoq-bestandens brug af landskabet på et tidspunkt, hvor det centrale område endnu ikke er påvirket af menneskelig aktivitet som f.eks. infrastruktur. Undersøgelsens resultater svækkes dog af en kort undersøgelsesperiode og en lille prøvestørrelse (som yderligere forværres af en høj mortalitet blandt individerne med halsbånd). Det er dyrt og vanskeligt at få positionsdata fra rensdyr i Grønland, men hvis der skal drages sikre konklusioner er det nødvendigt at indsamle data fra et stort og stabilt antal rensdyr over en længere periode.

Simler i Akia-Maniitsoq-bestanden opfører sig nogenlunde som den øko-type af rensdyr, der holder til i fjeldområder snarere end den type, der findes i tundraegne. Kælvningen var ikke begrænset til særlige kælvningsområder nær indlandsisen, men fandt sted over en større del af det centrale område, fra kysten til indlandsisen. Det giver derfor ikke mening at beskytte særlige kælvningsområder i Akia-Maniitsoq-området. Bestanden kunne derimod have gavn af en bredere habitatforvaltning, der tager de vidt udstrakte kælvningshabitater i betragtning.

Højde over havet var en god indikator for sandsynligheden for tilstedeværelse af simler i kælvningsperioden. Simler foretrak sydvendte skråninger med sne i ca. 600 meters højde (ligeegyldigt om skråningerne befandt sig i tørre eller fugtigere områder). De drægtige simlers valg af område kan skyldes timing i forhold til fremspirende vegetation og muligvis undvigelse af regn, men disse forhold er endnu ikke undersøgt til fulde. Akia-Maniitsoq-bestanden kælver tilsyneladende tidligere end antaget; derfor bør den periode, der er omfattet af beskyttelsesforanstaltninger, måske rykkes frem.

Udbredelse af kælvningshabitater er en vigtig faktor for rensdyrs produktion. Det synes dog ikke at være en begrænsende faktor for Akia-Maniitsoq-bestanden, da 42-45 % af Midtregionen omfatter områder, der er egnet til kælvning. Simler er imidlertid meget tro mod steder, hvor de tidligere har kælvnet, hvorfor et varmere klima eller menneskeskabte ændringer, der tvinger simlerne mod områder, der er mindre egnede for kalvenes overlevelse, kan have negative konsekvenser.

Dødeligheden var høj blandt simler, der var udstyret med satellithalsbånd. Det skyldtes tilsyneladende hovedsageligt jagt, som også kunne have spillet en stor rolle i faldet i Akia-Maniitsoq-bestandens størrelse fra 2001-2010, hvis hele bestanden har været påvirket på samme måde.

Analyse af årlige bevægelsesmønstre bekræftede tilstedeværelsen af en sydvest-nordvest-gående akse. Dyr bevægede sig ofte over korte afstande, og individer opholdt sig typisk i den vestlige end af akse om vinteren og i den østlige om sommeren; de enkelte simler brugte en brøkdel af det tilgængelige område. Det tyder stærkt på en underopdeling af bestanden i Midtregionen, hvorfor tilfældige vejrphenomener eller forvaltningsmæssige påvirkninger, som kun påvirker en del af området, muligvis ikke vil påvirke hele bestanden.

Analyse af årstidsvariationer i aktivitet afslørede 10 sæsonmæssige aktivitetsperioder, der hang sammen med særlige forhold i habitatet. Den primære

faktor, der varierede signifikant over årets aktivitetsperioder, var højden over havet. Rensdyrene formerer sig i lavtliggende områder og er derved relativt tilgængelige for jægere. Hvis jagtsæsonen falder sammen med brunstperioden, kan menneskelig aktivitet også virke forstyrrende og påvirke kalveproduktionen negativt.

Daglige bevægelsesmønstre varierede gennem året. Simler bevægede sig mindst i marts (optimalt for tælling fra luften) og mest i juli – sandsynligvis pga. insektplage, hvilket understreger nødvendigheden af simlers adgang til områder uden stikkende eller bidende insekter. I kælvningsperioden sås et karakteristisk dagligt bevægelsesmønster, som antageligt markerer en kælvning, dvs. en aktivitetsstigning i forhold til normalen umiddelbart forud for et skarpt fald til næsten nul efterfulgt af en gradvis stigning. Denne sammenhæng kan be- eller afkræftes ved at lokalisere simler med satellithalsbånd fra fly eller helikopter eller ved at udstyre simler med halsbånd med videokamera.

Habitatkaraktistika varierer meget over Midtregionen. De områder, der er til rådighed som sensommer-, efterårs- og vinterhabitater, er små i kontrast til kælvningshabitaternes størrelse og i forhold til hele Midtregionens størrelse. Dette kan være begrænsende for Akia-Maniitsoq-bestanden. Akia-lavlandet er småt, men det udgør det største område med vinterhabitat og er specielt sårbart over for sydvestlige storme, som kan gøre vinterfoder utilgængeligt eller vanskeligt at nå. Det kan derfor være på sin plads at give området speciel opmærksomhed eller beskyttelse gennem habitatforvaltning på en finere skala. Akia-Maniitsoq-bestanden vil sandsynligvis har gavn af, at rensdyrene sikres adgang til disse begrænsede habitater, at forstyrrelse fra menneskelig aktivitet holdes nede, og tætheden af rensdyr holdes under områdernes bæreevne.

Forvaltning skal helst skræddersys til bestanden, årstidsvariationer i den aktivitet, der er tale om, og udbredelse og tilgængelighed af habitat for aktiviteten. Beskyttelsesforanstaltninger skal adressere ikke blot ét, men flere årstidsbestemte udbredelsesområder som giver ly for stikkende insekter og er afgørende for reproduktion og overlevelse. Beskyttelse af kælvende simler og deres kælvningsområder er ikke en engangskur, der sikrer, at rensdyrbestande er bæredygtige eller kan komme sig.

Rensdyr bevæger sig meget. Globalt set er det almindeligt, at rensdyr ændrer opholdsområde, selv når det gælder "hellige" kælvningsområder. Forvaltningen skal derfor overveje at bevare p.t. uudnyttede områder til muligt fremtidigt brug for rensdyr. Menneskelig indflydelse på landskabet er en faktor, der vides at kunne øge fald i en rensdyrbestands størrelse. I Nordamerika forslås det, at 65 % af en rensdyrbestands totale udbredelsesområde skal forblive frit for menneskelig forstyrrelse, hvis bestanden skal bevare sin størrelse. Rensdyrbestande kan beskyttes nu og sikres for fremtidige generationer ved at bevare store intakte og uforstyrrede landskaber, som er afgørende for rensdyrenes aktiviteter og bevægelse.

Introduction

The indigenous Akia-Maniitsoq (AM) caribou population are classified the same subspecies as Canadian barren-ground caribou (*Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus*). They inhabit the Central region (Fig. 1, 2) and are the second largest population in West Greenland (Cuyler *et al.* 2011). Late winter population structures in 1998 and 2000 resulted in calf recruitments (calves/100 cows) of 65 and 49 respectively. In 2001 abundance was estimated at approximately 46,200 and calf recruitment 31 (Cuyler *et al.* 2003). In March 2010 it was estimated at approximately 24,000 individuals with late winter calf recruitment of approximately 23 (Cuyler *et al.* 2011). These numbers reflect a steady decline in both AM calf recruitment and population size since the turn of the century. The AM decline is unique since three other populations in West Greenland were relatively stable for the same period (Cuyler *et al.* 2011, 2016). Possible factors contributing to AM's decline would include, weather events, pathogens, forage condition and hunter harvest.

Large herbivore range use is typically seasonal, which involves movement corridors and areas essential to species sustainability. The latter are necessary for survival or population recovery. These may require special management or protection (Anon 1999), but must first be identified before management strategies can succeed. Prerequisite to delineating essential habitat is determining annual activity periods. Activity periods for caribou (*Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus*) have been defined by changes in movement, snow conditions, and from plant and insect phenology (Russell *et al.* 1993) or activity patterns (Maier & White 1998). While Ferguson & Elkie (2004) defined activity periods for boreal caribou (*R. t. caribou*) by applying regression analyses, both linear and polynomial, on movement data. It is recognized that the timing and duration of activity periods may differ among subpopulations within ecotype ranges (Maier & White 1998). Once activity periods are known, resource selection function models can assess the availability of high probability of use habitat during each activity period. To date, identification of Greenland caribou habitat has been limited to the summer season (Tamstorf *et al.* 2005, Simonsen 2011). Knowledge is sparse concerning activity periods and the distribution, quantity and attributes of seasonal habitats.

Fluctuating juvenile survival can affect the population dynamics of a species through decreased recruitment and cohort effects (Gaillard *et al.* 1998). For ungulates, essential habitats include calving sites because these provide

favorable conditions for calf survival (White 1983, Fancy & Whitten 1991). Calving strategies aim at maximizing survival of new offspring, and may include shifts in latitude or elevation to reduce predation risk, reproductive synchrony to achieve predator satiation, or prioritize access to emergent food resources and green-up (Bergerud & Page 1987, Fryxell *et al.* 1988, Klein 1990, Albon & Langvatn 1992, Post *et al.* 2003, Loe *et al.* 2005). Calving phenology is generally synchronous within populations and closely related to photoperiod as well as the onset and duration of plant growth (Post 2003). It is also affected by length and harshness of the previous winter (Tveraa *et al.* 2013). Since caribou are 'capital' breeders, i.e., parturient cows depend on body reserves rather than forage, peak parturition can precede green-up by several weeks (Durant *et al.* 2005, Moen *et al.* 2006, Barboza & Parker 2008, Taillon *et al.* 2013). Because strategies vary somewhat even among *Rangifer*, understanding the specific criteria that characterize habitat vital for calving in West Greenland is important for conservation measures to have an influence on abundance.

Figure 1. Map of entire Akia-Maniitsoq region, an area of ca. 15,400 km². Elevations above 200 meters are light yellow while those below are green.

Although central Alaska and Yukon caribou typically exhibit synchronous and long 300-500 km north-south migrations, with annual distances travelled ranging to 5000 km (Craighead & Craighead 1987, Fancy *et al.* 1989), West Greenland caribou resemble the mountain/forest dwelling sedentary caribou ecotype, because aggregations are absent and movements short (50-60 km) and non-synchronous (Cuyler & Linnell 2004). Previously, they were assumed to have west-east seasonal migrations between the seacoast (winter) and Greenland Ice Cap (summer) when abundance was high, and shortened migrations or none at all if low (Vibe 1967, Grønnow *et al.* 1983, Thing 1984). Certainly, Greenland caribou summer range can be inland near the Ice Cap; however, winter range can be intermediate between Ice Cap and seacoast (Cuyler & Linnell 2004). Meanwhile, regionally relevant studies are lacking.

Figure 2. Akia-Maniitsoq study area, 11,969 km², previously known calving areas, ● Cuyler and Linnell (2004), ● Cuyler unpublished, 2004 brown lines (Aastrup and Nymand 2004), 2015 stippled brown (NunaGis 2015). Elevations below 200 m are green, above 200 m yellow.

Although AM caribou are present throughout the Central region, calving locations are not adequately known. Throughout North America, barren-ground caribou populations usually have one well identified traditional calving ground, a sub-area of the total range for a specific population (Russell *et al.* 2002). A calving ground is a specific exclusive area where 80-90% of parturient cows return annually to calve (Gunn & Miller 1986), but may

change in spatial location over time (Gunn *et al.* 2008, Taillon *et al.* 2012). Identifying calving grounds for AM caribou has been elusive; although Strandgaard *et al.* (1983) suggested AM calving occurred in the northern inland portion of the range. In the Kangerlussuaq-Sisimiut caribou population to the north, large calving cow aggregations in close proximity to the Greenland Ice Cap were documented by Thing (1984). Subsequent studies for Greenland calving grounds focused on inland areas and observed cows calving (Aastrup 1986; Aastrup & Nymand 2004; J. Nymand, Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, unpublished data). Meanwhile, hunter knowledge for AM indicated a small rugged highland area near the AM seacoast (200-500 m elevation; 65° 23' N; 51° 40' W). Further, eight satellite-collared AM cows, 1997-1999, were highly dispersed in the calving season (Cuyler & Linnell 2004), not restricted to areas close to the Ice Cap, were typically at elevations above 300 m (Fig. 2) and exhibited 88% fidelity among sequential birthing sites (Cuyler & Linnell 2004). Site fidelity (philopatry) is the tendency of an animal to stay in, or habitually return to, a specific site or area. These attributes are similar to the mountain caribou ecotype (Bergerud *et al.* 1984, Skogland 1989). Nevertheless, there was just one small inland calving ground officially recognized for protection (Aastrup & Nymand 2004). Although this calving ground was expanded by 2015 (<http://www.nunagis.gl>), it remained a specific area associated with the period 20 May to 20 June (Government of Greenland Bureau of Minerals and Petroleum 2000) and human activities have been regulated accordingly.

Seasonal habitats have been hitherto poorly understood and knowledge insufficient to provide a firm basis for management recommendations that can meet future challenges e.g., stochastic weather events, infrastructure developments, pathogens, or any combination of these and other factors.

Present Study

In early May 2008, we deployed GPS satellite collars on 40 caribou cows of the AM population and followed these until July 2010. We delineated mean daily movement over a 1-year cycle and extent of migratory path. We examined the seasonal activity periods of Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows and describe the habitat attributes associated with those activity periods. We investigated and mapped the location and availability of the habitat attributes and probability of caribou cow occurrence for a given activity period. We delineate movement patterns associated with calving sites, timing of calving period, calving locations, and cow fidelity to calving sites. We determined whether areas

used by caribou during calving have characteristics that are uniquely different from those used during rest of the year. Environmental conditions were considered. Since adult female survival is a key determinant of ungulate population dynamics, mortality among the satellite-collared cows is addressed. Since securing sufficient habitat could facilitate conservation of AM caribou, we delineate which seasonal ranges are both essential and limited in availability.

Methods

Study area

The Central region (hunting area 3) of West Greenland is centred at 65° 10' N; 51° 25' W north of Nuuk, and is ca. 15,400 km². Our study area, a sub-set of the total region (Figs. 1, 2), was 11,969 km² and excluded the heavily glaciated northwest, as well as lakes, glaciers and sand. The surrounding ocean, fjords and glaciers restrict dispersal of caribou from the region, creating a largely "closed" population. The region is primarily rugged uplands and mountains, elevations ≥ 300 m cover 60%, 200-300 m cover 8% and under 200 m 32%. The region is undeveloped and lacks infrastructure. During the study period, 2008-2010, the backcountry was inaccessible to the majority of people. Most were limited to boating along the coast and fjord shorelines, and hiking into the terrain seldom was beyond about 6 km. Other than caribou, mammals present are few and include only the arctic hare (*Lepus arcticus*) and arctic fox (*Alopex lagopus*) as well as introduced feral reindeer (1952) (*R. t. tarandus*) and the recently arrived muskoxen (*Ovibos moschatus*; natural immigration since ca. 1998 from the Kangerlussuaq population north of Sukkertoppen Ice Cap). Large predators are absent; however, there is an annual caribou harvest. The region is sandwiched between a dominating high pressure over the Greenland Ice Cap to the east and frequent low-pressure oceanic storm systems (wind speeds 22–46 m/sec) from the southwest (Tamstorf 2004, DMI 2014, Gamberg *et al.* 2016). Precipitation decreases strongly with distance from the seacoast, resulting in a xeric continental climate near the Ice Cap (Tamstorf 2004). The nearest meteorological station is immediately south in the seacoast city of Nuuk, which has an annual mean temperature of -1.4°C, mean July 6.5°C and receives an annual precipitation of 752 mm (Tamstorf *et al.* 2005, DMI 2014). Vegetation is chiefly low-arctic species. Plant communities vary with elevation, aspect, and proximity to influences of Greenland's wet coastal maritime and dry continental ice cap climates (Lund

et al. 2004, Simonsen 2011). The Akia coastal lowlands consist primarily of lichen-rich dwarf shrub heath, which moving inland changes to dwarf shrub heath with increasing grassland. In higher elevations windswept ridges, abrasion plateaus and bare ground dominate (Tamstoft 2004). The dominant plant species in our vegetation classes follows Bay & Simonsen (2009). Detailed descriptions of vegetation are in Lund *et al.* (2004) and Simonsen (2011). Vegetation and snow maps and digital terrain models are in Tøttrup (2009).

Caribou capture & telemetry

Cow caribou were captured 1-7 May 2008 with a net-gun fired from a helicopter. Satellite collars were deployed on 40 cows. There were 20 Telonics (Mesa, Arizona, USA and Service Argos, Landover, Maryland, USA) and 20 Iridium System Network (Vectronic Aerospace GmbH, Berlin Germany) global positioning system (GPS) satellite collars. Inter-location intervals for Telonics and Iridium collars were 1 hour (24 per day) and 2 hours (12 per day), respectively. All collars were programmed to release automatically after 108 -118 weeks. Locations from May 2008 to July 2010 were recorded as longitude and latitude coordinates and projected to the UTM Zone 22N Projected Coordinate System, WGS 1984 Geographic Coordinate System, Northern Hemisphere. For GIS analyses, we used ArcMap 10.1 (Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc., Redlands, California, USA). Caribou capture and collaring locations were spread throughout the Central region south of Sukkertoppen Ice Cap (Appendix 1). We identified cows by presence of vulva patch. Capture was close to calving and in AM cows abdominal swelling from winter rumen digesta/ contents is insignificant and late winter fat reserves among pregnant cows are generally zero (Cuyler unpublished data from 1996, 1997, 2008). Viewed from above, cows were assumed pregnant if the sides of the posterior half of their body protruded quite markedly relative to other cows. At capture, 38 of the 40 cows were ascertained pregnant (included a sub adult). Tooth eruption and wear determined age class (sub adult, adult). Cows collared in May 2008 included, 39 adults (age \geq 36 months) and one sub adult (35 months). The total number of GPS locations obtained in the 2008-2010 study period was 262,137.

Daily movements and migratory path length

We calculated the direct line distance (km) between all sequential locations per day for each caribou cow. Daily travel rates were standardized to the number of possible locations per day [sum of distances between locations

obtained/(no. locations obtained/no. locations possible per day)] and normalized using a \log_{10} transformation. Calculated distances provide a minimum estimate of total individual movement due to 1-2 hour gaps in telemetry.

We mapped paths to illustrate movement variation. All paths were created using Hawth's tools (Beyer 2007). We mapped the annual paths taken by each caribou each year. We summed daily path distances (km) to obtain annual mean total path distance, maximum and minimum. Longitudes / latitudes for the latter two provided the length of a cow's home range. We generated annual (calculated from the date of capture) minimum convex polygons (MCPs) and paths (straight-line distances between sequential locations) for each caribou using Hawth's Tools (Beyer 2007). We measured MCP areas and path lengths, standardized these to 365 days (areas or length divided by number of days tracked \times 365), and normalized them using a \log_{10} transformation. MCP areas and path lengths are influenced by sample size (Borger *et al.* 2006).

Seasonal activity periods

We subdivided the calculated daily travel rate data into 73 5-day periods and used analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) pair-wise comparisons (SPSS 11.5, Chicago, Illinois, USA) to identify all sequential 5-day periods when movement rates were not significantly different. These gave the start and end dates for each seasonal activity period. We used the first and last known and estimated parturition and conception dates to define the calving and breeding periods respectively.

Habitat selection modelling

Herbivore movement rates (Nagy 2011) and habitat requirements for maintenance, growth, reproduction (Ferguson & Elkie, 2004; Gustine *et al.*, 2006; Horn & Rubenstein, 1984) vary seasonally (Maier & White, 1998). Animal habitat affinities are commonly quantified at landscape scales (Johnson *et al.* 2004) using data for a dependent variable: telemetry animal locations (use) and geographic information system (GIS) generated random locations (available), i.e. 10 random locations per animal location, with each random location sampled from within a circle that was centered on the preceding telemetry location, and having a radius equal to the distance between the preceding and next successive telemetry location. The independent predictor variables are habitat and topographic features thought

to influence habitat selected by the caribou (Table 1). The data for dependent and independent variables are used to construct resource selection functions (RSF) of the following form:

$$w(x) = \exp(\beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

(Johnson *et al.* 2004). The relative probabilities of occurrence of animals on landscapes are commonly calculated from RSFs and mapped using linear stretch transformations of the form:

$$\hat{w} = [(w(x) - w_{\min}) / (w_{\max} - w_{\min})] \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where $w(x)$ is the product of equation 1 and w_{\min} and w_{\max} represent the smallest and largest RSF values, respectively (Johnson *et al.* 2004). However, relative probabilities of occurrence assessments using this method are sensitive to the value of w_{\max} . Rare large values of w_{\max} may result in underestimation of the relative probabilities of occurrence and affect the reliability of k-fold cross-validation techniques typically used to assess the predictive performance of RSF models (Boyce *et al.* 2002). The consequences of underestimating habitat values in an area may be significant for conservation and management.

We assumed that the attributes (e.g., elevation, vegetation cover types, wind-exposure) of sites selected by Greenland caribou varied seasonally, to address their changing physiological requirements and behaviors. Therefore, we first identified their activity periods based on significant changes in daily movement rates (Nagy 2011). We used a moving-window GIS approach to assess the presence/absence of 11 vegetation cover types and average elevation within a 0.02 km² area around each caribou (use) and random (available) location. We used logistic regressions (equation 1) to fit RSF models for each activity period (Johnson *et al.* 2004, Latham *et al.* 2011) and selected the best-fitting models using Schwarz information criteria (SBIC) (Cook 2007, Hardin & Hilbe 2012, Schwarz 1978, Strong *et al.* 1999, Wasser *et al.* 2011). To calculate relative probabilities of caribou occurrence (w) (equation 3) we modified equation 2. Rather than w_{\max} we used the w_{median} RSF values for caribou use locations within the study area for each activity period using the following modified linear stretch transformation:

$$\hat{w} = [(w(x) - w_{\min}) / (w_{\text{median RSF caribou locations}} - w_{\min})]. \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

We used $w_{\text{median RSF caribou locations}}$ under the assumption that at least 50 percent of the caribou locations obtained during any activity period should be in preferred habitats. This method allows for replicable mapping of RSF models and comparisons of relative probability of occurrence among seasonal models. We partitioned \hat{w} into three equal intervals of relative probability of occurrence categories: A) ≤ 0.333 (low), B) > 0.333 and ≤ 0.666 (moderate), and C) > 0.666 (high). We calculated the percent of locations that fell within each probability of occurrence category to quantify the known frequency of use of areas we mapped as high, moderate, and low probability of occurrence. We obtained relative probability of occurrence for a specific activity period by pooling data for all years for that activity period.

Table 1. Labels & definitions¹ for resource selection (RS) habitat and elevation covariates considered in seasonal RS models for West Greenland Akia-Maniitsoq satellite-collared caribou cows.

Covariate	Definition
Elevation	Continuous variable; maximum elevation in meters above sea level (m asl) within focal area*.
Heath	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by willow (<i>Betula nana</i>), crowberry (<i>Empetrum nigrum hermaphroditum</i>), blueberry (<i>Vaccinium uliginosum microphyllum</i>), and Labrador tea (<i>Ledum groenlandicum</i> , <i>Ledum palustre decumbens</i>).
Open heath	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by blueberry (<i>Vaccinium uliginosum microphyllum</i>), birch (<i>Betula nana</i>), heather (<i>Cassiope tetragona</i> , <i>Phyllodoce coerulea</i>), and Labrador tea (<i>Ledum palustre decumbens</i>).
Copse	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by willow (<i>Salix glauca</i>).
Fen	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by fireweed (<i>Eriophorum angustifolium hyparcticum</i>) and sedges (<i>Carex rariflora</i>).
Grass	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by grasses (<i>Calamagrostis lapponica/groenlandica</i>), sedges (<i>Carex brunnescens</i> , <i>Carex bigelowii</i>), bunch grasses (<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>), and wood rushes (<i>Luzula spicata</i>).
Snow-bed	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by willows (<i>Salix herbacea</i>) and sedges (<i>Carex bigelowii</i>).
Wind-exposed	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Vegetation dominated by mosses, lichens, dwarf shrubs (<i>Diapensia lapponica lapponica</i>), Labrador tea (<i>Ledum palustre decumbens</i>), campion (<i>Silene acaulis</i>), sweet grass (<i>Hierochloë alpine</i>), sedges (<i>Carex bigelowii</i>), and rhododendrons (<i>Rhododendron lapponica</i>).
Soil / Rock	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Exposed soil and rock.
Sediment	Discrete variable; present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. River, estuarine, or coastal flood plains.
Water	Discrete variable present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Fresh water lakes, rivers, and streams.
Snow / Ice	Discrete variable present (1) or absent (0) within focal area. Persistent multi-annual snow and ice.

¹ Bay & Simonsen 2009; Simonsen 2011

*Focal area is the 5x5 30 m cell moving window around each 30 m cell.

Model construction: animal locations & environmental covariates

We derived the 12 independent variables (also termed covariates) from Tøttrup's (2009) 30 m resolution satellite image based digital habitat and elevation models (Table 1), which included heath, open-heath, copse, fen, grass, snow-bed, wind-exposed, soil or rock, sediment, water, snow or ice (Bay & Simonsen 2009; Simonsen 2011) and elevation. We used ArcMap to create a separate 30 m cell-size grid for each independent variable. Habitat grid cells were assigned values of 1 or 0 if habitats were present or absent, respectively. We used a moving window, 5x5 30 m cell, in GIS, to determine the presence (1) or absence (0) of habitats within an area of $\approx 0.02 \text{ km}^2$ surrounding each 30 m grid cell (focal cell) of each habitat grid. Focal cells were reclassified as having no data if clouds or shadows occurred in $>20\%$ of the cells contained in the moving window. We assigned the maximum elevation within moving windows for the elevation grid focal cells. We used GIS to extract the value for each focal habitat and elevation grid cell to intersect caribou and random locations (generated at a rate of 1 per km^2 in the study area).

Resources selection analysis

Data for each female were sub-sampled randomly to one location per day (of the most accurate locations). 19,572 locations (one location per day per female) were used to calculate resource selection functions. We assessed patterns of habitat selection at the population level (Johnson *et al.* 2004; Latham *et al.* 2011), i.e., at the scale of the landscape within the study area, by comparing habitats and elevations at caribou GPS (used) and random (available) locations with used-versus-available design logistic regressions for each seasonal activity period (Johnson *et al.* 2006, Manly *et al.* 2002). We used GLM logit STATA 9 (STATCORP, College Station, Texas, USA) to assess the relationship between use and availability of all possible combinations of the 12 explanatory variables and selected the best-fitting models (Cook 2007, Hardin & Hilbe 2012, Schwarz 1978, Strong *et al.* 1999, Wasser *et al.* 2011) for each seasonal activity period using Schwarz's information criteria (SBIC) (STATA 9; Schwarz 1978). We mapped the probability of occurrence of caribou using our modified linear stretch transformation (equation 3).

Assessment of habitat selection among activity periods

We compared relative selection of habitat types by caribou during calving and all other activity periods using logistic regressions to estimate coefficients for latent selection difference (LSD) functions (Czertwytynski 2007, Latham *et al.*

2011, Mueller *et al.* 2004). We used ANOVA and Tukey's honestly significant different (HSD) pairwise comparisons to determine if elevations at caribou locations varied significantly among activity periods. We \log_{10} transformed elevation data prior to conducting ANOVA and back-transformed the resulting statistics for interpretation.

Calving

Parturition (calving site): movement patterns

Cervids commonly exhibit marked (i.e., > 50%) declines in daily movements immediately following parturition (Long *et al.* 2009). An abrupt lack of movement is evident when caribou birth their calf; cows stop completely (Lent 1966). Following birth of the neonate, directional movement is absent for several hours and thereafter; if it occurs, it is slow with many pauses (Lent 1966). More recently, Ferguson & Elkie (2004) observed that a sedentary period of low movement rate maintained for about 3 days affirmed calving in woodland caribou (*Rangifer tarandus caribou*). Using this knowledge and daily movement rates in the ± 10 days around the date a cow stopped completely Nagy (2011) ascertained date of birthing for 336 cows, which was validated by visual survey. Criteria included daily movement rates rising sharply for several days, then falling precipitously to near zero, with a gradual increase in the days following.

We predicted parturition dates using the above. We calculated daily travel rate by each caribou cow during the 15 April - 15 July maximum range of potential calving dates, and assumed that the date of the abrupt fall/cessation in daily movement signaled a birthing event, while the associated GPS location provided the calving site point data.

Calving period & cow fidelity to calving site

In addition to mean calving date, we defined periods of 'most' and 'peak' calving to augment assessment of possible temporal variations. The period of 'most' calving was estimated to be within ± 1.96 standard deviation (SD; 95% CI) of the mean parturition date, and 'peak' calving to be within ± 1 SD (68% CI) (Nagy 2011). We estimated conception dates by back-dating 229 days from parturition dates (Bergerud 1975, McEwan & Whitehead 1972, Rowell & Shipka 2009). We used the first and last estimated parturition and conception dates to define the start and end dates for the calving and breeding periods, respectively. Although the number of collared cows declined steeply over the study period, we still attempted to examine whether the period of calving

varied significantly among years by using analyses of variance ([ANOVA]; SPSS 11.5, Chicago, Illinois, USA).

Using the central GPS location on the ascertained day of parturition (birthing) as the calving site point data, we calculated cow fidelity to a calving site as the distance (km) among sequential calving sites. To assess cow fidelity to previous calving sites, we compared sequential calving sites for each cow.

Elevation, winter snow, aspect and slope at calving sites

Caribou cows are capital breeders, i.e., birthing and nursing prior to green-up (Durant *et al.* 2005, Moen *et al.* 2006, Barboza & Parker 2008, Taillon *et al.* 2013), and birthing sites are assumed to provide advantages for calf survival (White 1983, Fancy & Whitten 1991). Already in the 1990's, Greenland cows in the calving period were known to choose elevations over 300 m (Cuyler & Linnell 2004). Assuming elevation use is related to the timing of spring arrival, birthing sites were examined by specific elevation chosen and whether winter snow persisted, and additionally to aspect and slope. We linked calving site point data (n= 52) to spatial and temporal environmental variables that were assessed from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer [MODIS] at the Terra and Aqua National Aeronautics and Space Administration [NASA] satellite platforms (Hall *et al.* 2014) downloaded from <http://nsidc.org/data>. These provided daily snow presence or absence at a resolution of 500 m. Where data was unavailable, we used nearby values within 1-3 km or adjacent 1-4 days. Calving site point data (locations) were analyzed for terrain morphology at a resolution of 30 m x 90 m: elevation (metres above sea level) calibrated to the region's Mean Sea Level, compass direction aspect, and terrain steepness in grade degrees. These were extracted from General Image Manipulation Program [GIMP] digital terrain model, Byrd Polar and Climate Research Center, Ohio State University (Howat *et al.* 2014) and data prepared and queried using GDAL 1.11 and QGIS 2.6.1. To test whether yearling-at-heel status (presence, absence) of a parturient cow affected cow choice of calving site, yearling-at-heel status was noted at capture and considered for the 2008 calving season.

Mortality

Mortality was assumed when collar locations became stationary. For the many collars that were not recovered, we do not know if a hunter harvested a cow and left the collar, or if the cow died of natural causes. However, hunter harvest could be assumed, if typical animal movement locations ceased

abruptly followed by rapid direct movement to a fjord or seacoast shoreline that same day, with subsequent movement on a fjord or ocean surface (e.g., by boat), with the final destination a human habitation, where the signal remained thereafter.

Table 2. Mortality among satellite-collared Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland between 2008 and 2010.

Year	Period	Number cows		Mortality			
		Start	End	Natural	Harvest	Total	% annually
1	1 May – 31 Dec 2008	40	27	4	9	13	32.5
2	1 Jan – 31 Dec 2009	27	15	6	6	12	44.4
3	1 Jan – 5 July 2010	15	14	1	n/a	1	6.6*
TOTALS				11	15	26	

*Period only 6 months and ended prior to annual harvest. n/a = not applicable.

Table 3. Mean and total number of locations obtained for tracked females and activity periods, respectively, 2008-2010.

Activity period	# cows	Mean no. locations	Total no. locations
		per cow	per period
Calving	40	968	38704
Post-calving	39	276	10764
Early/mid-summer	39	816	31817
Mid/late summer	38	536	20383
Fall/pre-breeding	38	483	18343
Breeding	37	748	27662
Late fall/early winter	32	700	22415
Mid-wiinter	29	1739	50419
Late winter	26	862	22424
Pre-calving	40	480	19206

Results

Mortality

The original 40 collared caribou cows declined in number over 2-years until 14 collared cows remained by spring 2010 (Table 2). The 26 deaths represent 65% mortality among collared cows. 15 were attributed to autumn hunter harvest, evidenced by GPS positions bee-lining to a coast and speeding along fjords to human habitation, or collar recovery where nothing remained but hide. Although not 100% certain, 11 were attributed to natural causes, because the deaths were outside hunting seasons and typically, the daily movements shortened gradually until they ceased. Thus, harvest may represent 58% and natural causes 42% of all mortalities. Mortalities attributed to harvest

occurred in September, October and November (Fig. 3). Of the 11 assumed natural mortalities, six took place in June - July, while four occurred in early winter, and one in late winter.

Figure 3. The 26 mortalities among satellite-collared caribou cows from the Akia-Maniitsoq population in West Greenland 2008-2010. Autumn harvest accounted for 15 deaths, while 11 were assumed due to natural causes.

Migratory path length & daily movement

For the satellite-collared AM caribou cows with full years of data (n=25), Table 2, Fig. 3), cumulative annual movement path distances (Fig. 4) were a mean 777 km ± 395, with a maximum of 1577 km, minimum 94 km. Extent of home ranges had a mean of 76 km ± 34 SD, with maximum of 143 km and minimum of 20 km. The log transformed mean daily movement (Fig. 5) indicates lowest movement activity in March, highest activity in July and a small peak in late September.

Seasonal activity periods

We identified 10 caribou activity periods based on significant changes in daily movement rates (data not shown) including calving, post-calving, early/mid-summer, mid/late summer, fall/pre-breeding, breeding, late fall/early winter, mid-winter, late winter, and pre-calving (Table 3). Seasonal activity period date ranges and durations (no. days) are given in (Table 4).

Landscape-scale habitat selection

The distribution of habitat type(s) present within, and mean elevations for focal grid cell in the study area (Fig. 6), illustrate that open-heath (65%), wind-exposed (52%), soil/rock (48%), and heaths (47%) were most frequently present within focal cells (Table 5) and were most widely distributed in the study area. We tested 297 different combinations of independent variables for each activity period. The most parsimonious models (i.e. the fewest variables to explain the greatest amount of variation, hereafter best-fit models) were those with the lowest Schwarz information criteria (SBIC) values. Covariates for the best-fit and the top 10 best-fit models for each activity period are listed in Table 6 and Appendix 2, respectively. The best-fit models for the calving, peak-calving, post-calving, early mid-summer, mid-/late summer, and breeding periods included all covariates. Best-fit models for fall/pre-breeding excluded the covariates elevation and open-heath, while those for late fall/early winter - pre-calving periods excluded covariate snow/ice (Table 7).

Assessment of habitat selection

Best-fit models suggested that at large spatial scales and throughout the year that caribou selected areas with copse, grass, and heath habitats that largely did not include soil/rock, water, and snow/ice (Tables 7 - 11). During post-breeding/late fall - post-calving and early/mid-summer - mid/late summer periods the sites selected also include open-heath and snow-bed habitats, respectively. Fen habitat was largely used in proportion to availability during all periods. Based on latent selection differences, during the calving period females were more likely to be associated with wind-exposed, open-heath, and water habitats than during all other activity periods (Table 12).

Habitat availability & use

Highly selected habitat attributes specific to a seasonal activity period were not equally distributed throughout the study area (Fig 7, Table 13). Habitat attributes chosen by caribou cows in fall/pre-breeding or late fall/early winter were the least available. Both were available in only 21% of the study area, followed by breeding (24%) and winter (mid-winter 26%, late winter 31%). Seasons with the most available attributes were early/mid-summer (51%) followed by the calving period (45%; for peak calving see Fig. 9). In descending order, the remaining seasonal activity periods were mid/late summer (35%), post-calving (39%) and pre-calving (43%).

Figure 4. Overview of movement paths for satellite-collared Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows 2008-2010. Sequential coloured circles represent tracked locations of individuals, one colour per animal. Some colours, however, were repeated if individuals were in widely different areas of the region.

Table 4. Seasonal activity periods as calculated from daily travel rates for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Activity period	Dates	No. days
Calving	11 May – 17 June	38
Post-calving	18 June – 3 July	16
Early/mid-summer	4 July – 2 August	30
Mid/late summer	3 August – 1 September	30
Fall/pre-breeding	2 September – 23 September	22
Breeding	24 September - 31 October	38
Late fall/early winter	1 November - 10 January	71
Mid-winter	11 January - 28 February	49
Late winter	1 March - 4 April	35
Pre-calving	5 April - 10 May	36
Total days		365

Figure 5. Mean daily movement by Julian day for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows.

Table 5. Availability of habitat types within 0.02 km² area around focal grid cells.

Habitat covariate (Independent variable)	Percent of focal cells habitat present (in rank order of present)	
	absent	present
Open-heath	35	65
Wind-exposed	48	52
Soil/rock	52	48
Heath	53	47
Water	72	28
Fen	73	27
Sediment	78	22
Grass	81	19
Copse	84	16
Snow-bed	91	9
Snow/ice	98	2

Figure 6. Distribution of habitat types present within 150x150 m moving window around each focal 30 m grid cell in the study area. Multi-year permanent snow/ice variable doesn't include Ice Cap.

Use/Available ratios

The ratios indicate when caribou use of a habitat was disproportionately less than, equal to, or greater than availability within the study area (<1.0, 1.0, and >1.0). The highest UA ratio was 3.33 during the late fall/early winter season (Table 13). Thus, cows were disproportionately selecting for this range in light of its low availability. The second highest UA was 3.03 and occurred during breeding. The third was fall/pre-breeding at 2.75 followed closely by mid-winter at 2.71. Thereafter came late winter and mid/late summer, both with UA's >2.0. Given that early/mid-summer range was the most available it was not surprising that it also had the lowest UA, 1.49.

Table 6. Best-fit activity period resource selection function models for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Activity period	Covariates in best-fit models	BIC
Calving	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-150298.7
Peak-calving	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137189.4
Post-calving	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-136853.8
Early/mid-summer	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140048.1
Mid/late summer	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140439.1
Fall/pre-breeding	heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137204.7
Breeding	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-143218.3
Late fall/early winter	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-154203.3
Mid-winter	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-144092.0
Late winter	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-139452.9
Pre-calving	elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137443.7

Table 7. Parameter estimates and standard errors in the best-fit calving and peak of calving (mean calving date ± 1 SD) activity period resource selection function models for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Habitat covariate	Calving Period (mean calving date ± 1.96 SD)			Peak calving (mean calving date ± 1 SD)		
	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value
Elevation	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000
Heath	0.487	0.057	0.000	0.294	0.084	0.000
Open-heath	0.661	0.061	0.000	0.429	0.086	0.000
Copse	0.870	0.061	0.000	0.889	0.090	0.000
Fen	-0.103	0.058	0.074	0.051	0.083	0.540
Grass	0.446	0.047	0.000	0.401	0.068	0.000
Snow-bed	-0.210	0.104	0.044	-0.010	0.152	0.950
Wind exposed	0.431	0.058	0.000	0.350	0.084	0.000
Soil/rock	-0.203	0.049	0.000	-0.223	0.072	0.000
Sediment	-0.238	0.070	0.001	-0.383	0.106	0.000
Water	-0.605	0.074	0.000	-0.907	0.116	0.000
Snow/ice	-1.275	0.329	0.000	-2.295	0.715	0.000
Intercept	-3.050	0.091	0.000	-3.734	0.132	0.000

Table 8. Parameter estimates and standard errors in the best-fit post-calving, early/mid-summer, and mid/late summer activity period resource selection function models for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Habitat covariate	Activity period								
	Post-calving			Early/mid summer			Mid/late summer		
	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value
Elevation	0.002	0.000	0.00	0.001	0.000	0.00	0.001	0.000	0.00
Heath	0.907	0.092	0.00	0.558	0.078	0.00	1.385	0.088	0.00
Open-heath	-0.002	0.083	0.98	-0.249	0.066	0.00	-0.073	0.069	0.29
Copse	0.884	0.086	0.00	0.974	0.075	0.00	0.794	0.068	0.00
Fen	0.017	0.086	0.85	0.111	0.070	0.11	0.037	0.072	0.60
Grass	0.290	0.071	0.00	0.276	0.063	0.00	0.254	0.063	0.00
Snow-bed	0.235	0.142	0.10	0.380	0.104	0.00	0.289	0.103	0.01
Wind exposed	0.391	0.083	0.00	0.195	0.071	0.01	-0.321	0.070	0.00
Soil/rock	-0.324	0.076	0.00	-0.127	0.065	0.05	0.096	0.065	0.14
Sediment	-0.102	0.099	0.31	0.115	0.073	0.12	0.006	0.078	0.94
Water	-0.936	0.116	0.00	-0.749	0.084	0.00	-0.498	0.085	0.00
Snow/ice	-2.219	0.716	0.00	-1.260	0.329	0.00	-15.682	494.905	0.98
Intercept	-3.802	0.132	0.00	-2.903	0.104	0.00	-3.384	0.111	0.00

Table 9. Parameter estimates and standard errors in the best-fit fall/pre-breeding, breeding, and post-breeding/late fall activity period resource selection function models for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Habitat covariate	Activity period								
	Fall/pre-breeding			Breeding			Post-breeding/late fall		
	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value
Elevation	-	-	-	-0.002	0.000	0.00	-0.004	0.000	0.00
Heath	1.189	0.093	0.00	1.258	0.096	0.00	1.257	0.082	0.00
Open-heath	-	-	-	0.023	0.069	0.74	0.385	0.062	0.00
Copse	0.602	0.074	0.00	0.449	0.062	0.00	0.348	0.052	0.00
Fen	-0.155	0.089	0.08	-0.048	0.072	0.50	0.063	0.058	0.28
Grass	0.679	0.068	0.00	0.710	0.060	0.00	0.505	0.055	0.00
Snow-bed	-0.034	0.151	0.82	-0.288	0.128	0.03	-0.310	0.101	0.00
Wind exposed	-0.065	0.077	0.40	-0.391	0.070	0.00	-0.121	0.059	0.04
Soil/rock	-0.172	0.076	0.02	-0.080	0.067	0.23	-0.452	0.060	0.00
Sediment	-0.276	0.105	0.01	0.059	0.083	0.48	-0.040	0.069	0.56
Water	-0.555	0.112	0.00	-0.961	0.097	0.00	-0.656	0.076	0.00
Snow/ice	-14.893	510.544	0.98	-14.467	453.309	0.98	-	-	-
Intercept	-3.308	0.101	0.00	-2.253	0.111	0.00	-1.627	0.094	0.00

Table 10. Parameter estimates and standard errors in the best-fit early/mid winter, late winter, and pre-calving activity period resource selection models for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Habitat covariate	Activity period								
	Early/mid winter			Late winter			Pre-calving		
	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value	Parameter estimate	SE	P-value
Elevation	-0.003	0.000	0.00	-0.002	0.000	0.00	-0.001	0.000	0.00
Heath	0.901	0.079	0.00	0.950	0.091	0.00	0.274	0.082	0.00
Open-heath	0.653	0.076	0.00	0.304	0.079	0.00	0.529	0.087	0.00
Copse	0.397	0.061	0.00	0.505	0.069	0.00	0.435	0.079	0.00
Fen	0.132	0.063	0.04	-0.079	0.074	0.29	0.074	0.076	0.33
Grass	0.219	0.059	0.00	0.228	0.067	0.00	0.332	0.069	0.00
Snow-bed	-0.152	0.108	0.16	-0.408	0.133	0.00	-0.295	0.134	0.03
Wind exposed	0.383	0.063	0.00	0.348	0.073	0.00	0.446	0.077	0.00
Soil/rock	-0.305	0.061	0.00	-0.190	0.070	0.01	-0.442	0.071	0.00
Sediment	0.044	0.075	0.56	0.399	0.081	0.00	0.273	0.085	0.00
Water	-0.690	0.085	0.00	-0.661	0.095	0.00	-0.489	0.094	0.00
Snow/ice	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Intercept	-2.352	0.103	0.00	-2.631	0.113	0.00	-2.734	0.115	0.00

Table 11. Overview of habitat selection by seasonal activity period for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Seasonal Activity period	Resource selection function covariates*											
	elevation	heath	open-heath	copse	fen	grass	snow-bed	wind-exposed	soil/rock	sediment	water	snow/ice
calving	+	+	+	+	=	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
post-calving	+	+	=	+	=	+	=	+	-	=	-	-
early/mid summer	+	+	-	+	=	+	+	+	=	=	-	-
mid/late summer	+	+	=	+	=	+	+	-	=	=	-	=
fall/pre-breeding	excluded	+	excluded	+	=	+	=	=	-	-	-	=
breeding	-	+	=	+	=	+	-	-	=	=	-	=
post-breeding/late fall	-	+	+	+	=	+	-	-	-	=	-	excluded
early/mid winter	-	+	+	+	+	+	=	+	-	=	-	excluded
late winter	-	+	+	+	=	+	-	+	-	+	-	excluded
pre-calving	-	+	+	+	=	+	-	+	-	+	-	excluded

*+, =, and - denote covariate coefficients that were significant greater, not significantly different from, and significantly less than zero.

Table 12. Habitat selection during the calving period relative to those selected during all other activity periods based on latent selection difference (LSD) function model comparisons for Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Seasonal Activity Period	Relative selection*										
	Heath	Open-heath	Copse	Fen	Grass	Snow-bed	Wind-exposed	Soil/rock	Sediment	Water	Snow/ice
Post-calving	26	>100	=	=	=	31	=	=	=	>100	=
Early summer	=	>100	=	18	>100	=	>100	=	31	=	=
Mid/late summer	48	>100	=	=	=	39	>100	30	28	=	=
Fall/pre-breeding	51	>100	=	=	20	=	>100	=	=	=	=
Breeding	68	>100	=	=	17	=	>100	=	43	>100	=
Post-breeding/late fall	74	=	>100	29	=	=	>100	>100	46	>100	=
Early/mid winter	63	30	=	35	>100	=	>100	>100	47	>100	=
Late winter	62	=	=	17	>100	=	>100	=	59	>100	62
Pre-calving	=	=	>100	24	>100	=	>100	>100	49	=	=

*Relative selection was calculated for variables with coefficients significantly different from 0 as $\exp(b)$ when $b > 0$ and as $[1 - \exp(b)]$ when $b < 0$ (Latham, Latham & Boyce, 2011). Relative selection values < 100 indicate that use of the habitat during calving was significantly less by x% than that for the season being compared, values > 100 indicate use of habitat during calving was significantly greater than that for the season being compared, and = indicates habitat use during calving and season being compared were not significantly different (Appendix 3).

Table 13. Percent availability, percent use, and ratio of percent use: percent availability of areas by probability of occurrence category and activity period for Aki-Maniitsoq caribou cows in the Central region of West Greenland, 2008-2010.

Seasonal Activity period	Probability of occurrence								
	Percent of study area by occurrence category (Available)			Percent of caribou locations by occurrence category (Use)			U:A ratio for occurrence categories*		
	Low	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate	High	Low	Moderate	High
Calving	29	26	45	5	16	79	0.17	0.62	1.77
Post-calving	30	31	39	6	22	72	0.18	0.69	1.89
Early/mid summer	17	31	52	3	20	77	0.19	0.65	1.49
Mid/late summer	51	15	34	17	11	72	0.33	0.73	2.09
Fall/pre-breeding	57	22	21	16	26	58	0.28	1.18	2.75
Breeding	63	13	24	13	13	74	0.21	1.01	3.03
Late fall/early winter	67	12	21	12	19	69	0.18	1.56	3.33
Mid-winter	57	17	26	13	16	71	0.23	0.94	2.71
Late winter	53	16	31	13	12	75	0.24	0.75	2.44
Pre-calving	33	23	44	8	19	73	0.25	0.82	1.67

*U:A ratios <1.0, 1.0, and >1.0 indicate use was disproportionately less than available, proportional to availability, and disproportionately greater than availability.

Figure 7. Categorized probability of occurrence of Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in West Greenland during 10 activity periods: follow bold black arrows for annual cycle from calving to pre-calving. Maps represent the product of landscape-scale resource selection functions.

Elevation use relative to seasonal activity period

Mean elevation of caribou locations varied significantly among activity periods (ANOVA $F_{9,19562} 487.236$, $P < 0.001$). The following seasonal activities occurred in areas with decreasing elevation: calving and post-calving > early/mid-summer, mid-/late summer, fall/pre-breeding > pre-calving > breeding > late winter > mid-winter > late fall/early winter (Tukey's HSD pair-wise comparisons, $P < 0.05$). Areas used during the calving activity period and through mid/late summer were typically at higher elevation than those used during breeding-late winter (Tables 7 - 11; Fig. 7, 8). Specifically, calving and post-calving activities occurred at significantly higher elevations than all other activity periods, while late fall/early winter was lowest.

Figure 8. Elevation of sites used during seasonal activity periods by Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows in West Greenland, 2008-2010.

There were 38,704 GPS positions for the 2008-2009-2010 calving activity periods. The areas used by collared cows in the calving activity period analyzed for resource selection illustrated that cows selected ($P < 0.05$) for higher elevations. Overall, cows were more likely to be associated with high elevation wind-exposed areas near open-heath and water. At peak-calving

habitat criteria selected, in order of importance, were elevation, heath, open heath, copse, fen, grass, snow-bed and wind exposed ridge. The attribute combination for peak-calving is widely distributed throughout the Akia-Maniitsoq region and includes 5,027 km² (42%) of the total area (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. West Greenland Akia-Maniitsoq satellite-collared caribou, probability of cow occurrence during peak calving, 21 May to 8 June: High represents habitat typical for 72% (59-79%) of cow positions, moderate 17% (11-26%) and low 3-17%.

Figure 10. Distribution of the 52 calving sites 2008-2010 in relation to substrate, for the satellite-collared Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows West Greenland, lakes not shown. (Close proximity almost occludes three sites).

Calving sites

Elevation & snow at calving sites

There were 52 calving sites (51 adults, 1 sub adult). From the calving site point data, median elevation for all birthing adult cows was 593 m, mean $553 \text{ m} \pm 202 \text{ SD}$, minimum 144 m and maximum 962 m. The sub adult outlier birthed at 68 m in 2008, but as an adult at 300 m. For the spring 2008 calving season, the presence or absence of yearling-at-heel (calf from previous spring) was known. This had no effect on elevation chosen ($P = 0.059$, $df = 10$, $t = 2.2281$). However, we noted that the cows with yearling-at-heel ($n= 5$) on average birthed 132 m below cows without calves ($n=25$), 492.4 ± 107.1 and 624.0 ± 194.0 respectively (Table 14). Similarly, elevation was median 476 m,

maximum 648 m for cows with yearling-at-heel, and median 662 m, maximum 962 m for cows without. Perhaps something of biological significance is occurring, but it will require a larger sample size over multiple years to clarify.

Although median birthing elevation for adult cows was 593 m, substrates differed. 61% (n=31) of births took place where snow dominated the landscape (i.e., winter snow not yet melted by spring thaw) at median 637 m elevation, while 29% (n=15) birthed on bare ground median 593 m (Fig. 10). Unknown ground cover 10% (n=5), owing to clouds, coincided with lower elevations median 353 m (Table 15). Slope at sites was often < 20° grade. The majority of calving sites occurred on a 10° to 13° grade and had a generally southerly aspect. Although mean birthing date on snow substrate averaged 5 days earlier and at slightly higher elevations (ca. 80 m) than on bare ground, the difference was not significant ($P = 0.40$ and 0.11 respectively).

Table 14. Comparison of calving site conditions chosen by adult cows (n=30) relative to presence or absence of a yearling-at-heel, May-June 2008, Akia-Maniitsoq West Greenland.

Yearling-at-heel	n	Parturition mean \pm SD Julian date	Elevation mean \pm SD (m)	Calving median Julian date	Elevation median (m)	Aspect median (°)	Slope median (°)
Yes	5	151.6 \pm 10.6	492.4 \pm 107.1	154	476	191	16
No	25	153.0 \pm 5.6	624.0 \pm 194.0	153	662	164	8.1

Table 15. Comparison of calving site conditions chosen by adult cows (n =51; sub adult removed) 2008-2010, Akia-Maniitsoq West Greenland.

Calving site	n	Parturition mean \pm SD Julian date	Elevation mean \pm SD (m)	Calving median Julian date	Elevation median (m)	Aspect median (°)	Slope median (°)
Snow	31	150.5 \pm 8.4	592.2 \pm 195.6	150	637	187	10
Ground	15	154.1 \pm 6.3	536.9 \pm 211.2	155	593	221	13
Clouds	5	144.8	355.0 \pm 85.0	149	353	159	17

Figure 11a. Daily movement pattern of a parturient cow: steady low movement, then spike immediately preceding birthing (27 May 2008) when movement almost zero, subsequent gradually increasing daily movements. **11b.** Daily movement pattern of a non-parturient cow or possibly fetus / calf death, i.e. no discernible pattern.

Parturition movement pattern

It is widely accepted that cow movements approach zero on the day of parturition ((Lent 1966, Ferguson & Elkie 2004, Long *et al.* 2009, Nagy 2011). Thus we derived calving dates and locations for 2008, 2009 and 2010, for 31, 14, and 7 cows, respectively, for a total of 36 different cows and 52 birthing events/sites.

We observed the three classic movement states indicative of parturition (Ferguson & Elkie 2004, Long *et al.* 2009, Nagy 2011) among 31 pregnant-at-

capture cows during the immediately subsequent calving period. Movement states included, 1) rise in daily movement prior to calving date, 2) a precipitous decline in daily movement rates to near zero (median 131 m/day) indicative of a birthing event, and 3) a gradual increase in daily movement rates after calving date (Fig. 11a). Reproductive status of cows was considered unknown if they did not exhibit this movement pattern during the calving period, e.g., the two cows ascertained not pregnant at capture 2008 also had no discernible pattern or birthing event that calving season (Fig. 11b). At capture and collaring in 2008, 38 of the 40 cows were assessed pregnant (included a sub adult). However, during the 2008 calving period, only 31 of these evidenced the clear movement pattern indicating a birthing event. Capture occurred immediately preceding the calving period. The seven (18%) with no clear pattern may have lost their fetus, possibly as a direct result of capture trauma.

Assuming daily cow movement patterns accurately reflect birthing, reproductive pauses of typically 1-year seemed apparent. The high mortality among cows precluded any sweeping conclusions. Still, five of the cows that birthed in 2008 did not in 2009. Only one of these cows survived to 2010, when she again calved. Of the two cows that did not calf in 2008, one of them did in 2009. The other appeared to have a 2-year hiatus. Thirteen cows calved consecutively. Nine calved in the springs of both 2008 and 2009, and four calved first in 2009 and repeated again in 2010. Two cows calved in all three years. The relative number of cows evidencing the movement pattern associated with calving compared to cows with ambiguous patterns (unknown) or cows not calving (no calf) varied annually (Fig. 12).

Calving period

There were 52 parturition dates (Fig. 13). A sub adult outlier birthed 28 June in 2008. Calving dates for adult cows (n=51, 2008 sub adult removed) were normally distributed around the mean of 30 May \pm 8.2 days SD. Median calving was 31 May. Earliest and latest parturition dates for adult cows were 12 May and 13 June, respectively. The period of 'most' calving was estimated at 32 days, 14 May to 15 June (95% CI, i.e., mean \pm 1.96 SD). Period of 'peak' calving was estimated at 19 days, 21 May to 8 June (68% CI; i.e., mean \pm 1 SD). For the 2008 season, we compared the birthing dates of adult cows that had a yearling-at-heel from previous spring (n = 5) against those without (n= 25). The mean calving dates were similar ($P = 0.78$), or 31 May and 1 June respectively (Julian day 151.6 ± 10.6 and 153.0 ± 5.6).

Mean Julian calving dates for adult cows 2008, 2009, and 2010 were respectively, 152.80 ± 6.48 days (range 134-163; $n = 30$), 151.29 ± 10.45 (range 132-165; $n = 14$) and 142.86 ± 5.24 days (range 133-149; $n = 7$). Mean calving dates did not differ for 2008 and 2009, 2009 and 2010 (ANOVA $F_1 = 0.348$, $P = 0.558$; $F_1 = 3.98$, $P = 0.061$ respectively), however, a difference was observed between 2008 and 2010 (ANOVA $F_1 = 14.193$, $P = 0.006$). Employing the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test on calving dates resulted in no differences between 2008 and 2009, 2009 and 2010 ($P > 0.05$), but difference between 2008 and 2010 ($P \leq 0.001$). 2010 calving was approx. 10 days earlier than in 2008. Mean Julian calving dates for only those cows calving in the two specific years tested also tested non-significant for 2008 and 2009, 2009 and 2010 ($P > 0.05$). Comparison of cows birthing in both 2008 and 2010 was confounded by the small sample size of three and individual results of 15, 6 and -1 days, where 2010 calving was a mean 7 days earlier than in 2008 ($P > 0.05$).

Calving site fidelity

Although sample size was small and the study period short, we noted that calving site fidelity was high. There were 16 sequential calving locations for 14 cows (twelve cows had two locations; two cows had three). Median distance between sequential calving locations was 7.1 km. Mean distance was $12.5 \text{ km} \pm 11.7 \text{ SD}$, minimum was 0.5 km, and maximum 41.5 km. The minimum coincided with the cow that calved in 2008 and again in 2010, after a hiatus of one year.

Figure 12. Annual variation in the number of caribou cows in various reproductive states, 2008-2010.

Figure 13. Temporal distribution of 52 parturition dates 2008-2010, West Greenland Akia-Maniitsoq satellite-collared caribou cows (note 28 June sub adult outlier).

Discussion

The AM caribou are substantially less documented than caribou populations in North America. Therefore, this report could benefit caribou management in Greenland. Identifying the attributes, locations and extent of caribou seasonal habitats, and the timing of use of these, is indispensable to decisions intended to predict and offset negative impacts to caribou habitat, e.g., by climate and anthropogenic factors. The results presented in this report are particularly valuable because they establish a baseline for AM habitat use in the current absence of significant development and infrastructure in the Central region.

We do not advise extrapolating the current knowledge from AM to other populations in Greenland, owing to differences in population size, latitude, climate, topography and lack of seasonal habitat use data for the other populations. Further, the short study period and small sample size, which constantly diminished over that period, weaken this study's findings.

Akia-Maniitsoq cow movements

Daily

Similar to Cuyler & Linnell (2004) this study observed minimum daily movement/activity during a ca. 30-day period concurrent with March, specifically at the beginning of March. Highest cow movement rates occurred in July, and may be associated with insect harassment. The autumn rut

(breeding) created a second briefer peak in activity in late September. This knowledge indicates that aerial surveys for caribou abundance in early March will minimize the problem of caribou movement affecting the resulting population estimates.

The activity trend observed is not new. A summer activity increase has been observed for caribou / reindeer by several authors (Banfield 1954, Segal 1962, Thomson 1971, Gaare *et al.* 1975, White *et al.* 1975, and Roby 1977). The higher activity in summer is ascribed most often to high air temperatures and to biting and parasitic insects (Thing & Thing 1983, Mörschel & Klein 1997, Coleman *et al.* 2000) and it has been documented that wind speed affects mosquitoes, which have a threshold of 4-6 m/s (Russell *et al.* 1993, Parrot 2007). Increased caribou movement resulting from insect harassment reduces foraging time and negatively impacts calf growth and cow body condition (Mörschel & Klein 1997, Couturier *et al.* 2009). Thus insect relief habitat, i.e., windy locations and snow patches (Joly & Klein 2011, Wilson *et al.* 2012) is an important consideration when managing essential habitats.

Following parturition, it is typical among Cervids that there occurs an immediate and marked decline in daily movement (Long *et al.* 2009). The sudden cessation of movement at birthing by caribou cows was first described by Lent (1966), who observed that cows always stopped still when labour commenced, regardless if that cow had been with a moving group, which left the birthing cow behind. Ferguson & Elkie (2004) observed the same phenomenon, which was also later supported by Nagy's (2011) movement rates for cows around the time of calving and known to later have calves-at-heel (n=336). Still, an assumption that a cow being stationary equates with birthing requires further substantiation. Video collars, recording daily, on parturient cows would be one solution.

Annual

There was a distinct seasonal distribution of the collared caribou cows in the Central region. Generally, there was a southwest-northeast axis to their annual movements. Although movements were often short and normally not from seacoast to Ice Cap, each AM cow was typically furthest east in summer and furthest west in winter. Also, each cow utilized only a fraction of the available area. This supports Cuyler & Linnell's (2004) idea that there is a high degree of population sub-division of the AM caribou in the Central region. This knowledge is relevant for caribou management, e.g., conservation actions

applied to only a portion of the region will probably not benefit the entire population. Further, stochastic weather events, which have the potential for influencing caribou abundance negatively, if limited in extent to just a portion of the region, will also not likely affect the entire AM population.

Migratory path length

AM cow movements between winter and summer ranges were on a relatively small scale. The mean extent, 76 km, of AM cows' migratory path length was similar to that observed in the 1990's (Cuyler & Linnell 2004). In contrast, barren-ground caribou (same sub-species as AM cows), and those of northern Alaska, typically make long movements between winter and calving home ranges. These distances can be in the order of 300-500 km for the Central Alaskan or Porcupine herds (Craighead & Craighead 1987, Fancy *et al.* 1989) or many of the other herds in northern Canada (Hall 1989). On a geographic scale, the AM study area is much smaller than most North American migratory barren-ground caribou home ranges. Thus, our observed short AM migratory paths were not unexpected, and they illustrate the confined areas available to caribou in West Greenland. Also reflected is the diversity of habitats available to the AM caribou across relatively short distances. Since they do not traverse large distances, AM cows could partition any annual energy budget surplus to things other than locomotion, e.g., reproduction. This was supported in the 1990's when AM cows exhibited an exceptional lifetime fecundity (Cuyler & Østergaard 2005).

Movement of collared AM cows between winter and summer ranges was less than 100 km, followed an elevation gradient, and they were spatially independent from each other. Thus, AM cows appear unlike their barren-ground cousins and most similar to the Dolphin & Union Island, North American Boreal and Mountain Woodland Caribou *R. t. caribou* (Oosenburg & Theberge 1980, Bergerud *et al.* 1984, Skogland 1986, 1989, Edmonds 1988, Hillis *et al.* 1998, Nagy 2011, Nagy *et al.* 2011). This also highlights the importance of telemetry studies.

Seasonal activity periods

Individual caribou select habitat for their own successful survival and reproduction (Bélanger & Côté 2016, Fancy & Whitten 1991, Albon & Langvatn 1992). Patterns of movement revealed 10 seasonal activity periods for the Greenland AM population. These were associated with specific

habitat/range attributes. Our classification falls between Russell *et al.* (1993) who identified 15 activity periods for migratory barren-ground caribou, and Nagy's (2011) eight periods for both boreal caribou and tundra-wintering barren-ground caribou. Future analyses may reduce the partitioning to fewer than 10 periods, since for example the habitats chosen for early, mid and late winter periods appear similar.

Specific elevation use was associated with the different seasons throughout the year. Elevations under 200 m were always used for breeding through to the end of late winter, while elevations above 350 m were invariably used for calving and to the end of mid-summer. Elevation appeared to be a primary attribute defining seasonal ranges. This knowledge could be used for conservation actions, e.g., ending an autumn harvest before the onset of the breeding season, when caribou are at low elevations and accessible to hunters.

Late summer and fall ranges provide the basis for a caribou's body condition build-up that will permit participation in the rut (Cameron *et al.* 1993), while winter range is vital for survival (Bergerud *et al.* 2007). Thus these ranges qualify among the essential ranges for caribou, i.e., important for reproduction or survival. Unfortunately, for AM caribou, there is a scarcity of habitat area associated with late summer, fall and winter relative to the other periods. For example, preferred AM winter habitat use is at elevations under 200 m, and while winter range is vital for caribou survival, this habitat is in short supply for AM caribou. Winter range is the smallest area of all the seasonal ranges. AM winter range may therefore need special attention and protections. Increasing the concern, is that the largest tract of winter habitat, the Akia-Nordland lowlands north of Godthåbsfjord, is exposed to southwesterly storm systems. These bring the possibility of several negative weather events, e.g., deep snows, rain-on-snow, and icing. The shortage of late summer, fall and winter ranges, indicates that these could be limiting for the AM caribou population.

Seasonal habitat selection

Habitat selection varied by season, and seasonal habitats varied considerably in their distribution and area, relative to total study area. Calving habitat had the greatest area and distribution. Tied for the least area were fall/pre-breeding and late fall/early winter. In fact, for the activity periods from fall through mid-winter, habitats were relatively few and small in area. The

largest was the Akia-Nordland lowlands, followed by the smaller lowlands of the Narssarssuaq and Iluliak valleys. There were also a few scattered smaller valley lowlands. Taken together, they comprised only 21-26% of the total study area. The scarcity of these habitats emphasizes that human influences causing loss of these could have detrimental impacts on the AM population.

Interestingly, the fall/pre-breeding activity period evidenced the lowest percentage of cow locations even in the highest occurrence category. An earlier study observed that the lowest probability of occurrence for cows was at locations having the highest values of hunting (Simonsen 2011). Since fall/pre-breeding coincides with the hunting season (1 Aug – 30 Sept), results may reflect avoidance of disturbance / predation risk from hunters using the same areas. From a management perspective, this suggests that the human disturbance associated with a long summer/autumn harvest season may negatively influence breeding and subsequently calf production.

Our analyses for probability of cow occurrence during calving and breeding are supported by similar results obtained by Simonsen (2011). Our study, however, was able to identify more areas. As regards a comparison of summer and fall habitats, our probability of occurrence results suggest that fall [September] habitat/range is limited in area/availability, while summer [July] habitat/range is not. The small but important fall area suggests that fall habitat may require protection measures. This would be in addition to July habitat, which is important for among other things selective feeding by cows and insect relief (Tamstorf *et al.* 2005, Wilson *et al.* 2012). In the following sections, we will explore linkages among for example nutrition, forage, insect relief, elevation, hunting and winter snow.

Calving

Mean elevation use, ca. 400 m, in the calving activity period (11 May – 17 June) was significantly higher than for all other activity periods. Cuyler & Linnell (2004) and Simonsen (2011) also observed highest elevation use by AM cows during calving. Strikingly, calving sites themselves were typically at least 200 m above and beyond the mean elevation use for all cows in the calving activity period. This suggests that whatever benefits elevation confers, parturient cows appear to be maximizing these. Calving sites also had a generally southerly aspect, which would take advantage of solar radiation.

With the advent of reliable aspect models, future studies may be able to explore the significance of aspect on habitat selection at the landscape scale.

Similar to observations in the late 1990's (Cuyler & Linnell 2004), AM calving sites were dispersed in a continuum across the Central region, where the straight-line distance between seacoast and Greenland Ice Cap is only about 110 km. Certainly 1/3 of births occurred within 25 km of the Greenland Ice Cap, however, several were within 10-20 km of the seacoast. Only 4-5 sites corresponded with the 'calving ground' delineated in NunaGis (2015). Considering only inland areas, as suitable for calving, appears to have little relevance for AM cow habitat selection at calving. Cow dispersal at calving is typical for the montane ecotype of caribou (Bergerud *et al.* 1984, Skogland 1989) and once again, highlights how very unlike the AM caribou are from their barren-ground cousins. In contrast to proximity to the Ice Cap, elevation was the good predictor for probability of AM cow occurrence at calving (and breeding).

The AM calving continuum is unsurprising given that 42% of this range possesses the habitat attributes associated with highest probability of occurrence by cows during peak calving: high elevation, heath, open heath, copse, fen, grass, snowbed and wind exposed ridge. Potential xeric habitat for calving is present near the Ice Cap, but the extent of essential calving habitat available elsewhere throughout the region is now recognized. This strengthens capacity to regulate human activities in calving habitat before during and after calving.

Based on daily movement rates, the seasonal activity period for calving lasted from 11 May until 17 June. Using actual birthing events, 'Peak' calving (68%) was a 19-day period (21 May-8 June), with 'most' calving (95%) over a 32-day period, 14 May to 15 June. The period length of AM peak calving is similar to Boreal caribou (*R.t. caribou*) (Nagy 2011). May births were unexpectedly common, mean 30 May \pm 8.2 days. Genetic mixing with feral semi-domestic reindeer (Jepsen *et al.* 2002), which calf in May, is a plausible explanation for the early calving. Changing weather or plant phenology might also be factors. We note that mean calving date 2010 was 7-10 days earlier than 2008, however, the small 2010 sample size precludes conclusions about a forward shift in calving phenology.

Calving site fidelity

High fidelity to calving grounds illustrates their important role in the annual cycle of calf production (Gunn & Miller 1986, Fancy & Whitten 1991, Schaefer *et al.* 2000, Mahoney & Schaefer 2002, Russell *et al.* 2002, Ferguson & Elkie 2004). The satellite-collared AM cows exhibited high fidelity to previously chosen calving sites. However, our small sample size and short study period do not permit conclusive statements regarding patterns. It is interesting to note that our minimum value of 0.5 km and median value of 7.1 km were similar to the 4 to 11 km observed for caribou of the mountain ecotype in southeastern Labrador (Popp *et al.* 2011) and the < 5 km for woodland caribou of northern Ontario (Ferguson & Elkie 2004). In contrast, Yukon-Alaskan Porcupine caribou cows, which though faithful to a general area did not calve near same location annually, e.g., minimum 67.1 ± 49.1 km (Fancy & Whitten 1991). Given the high fidelity shown by AM cows, anthropogenic disturbance could have strong negative impacts if cows are forced to reduce fidelity to preferred sites (Faille *et al.* 2010).

Calving site choice

Spring migration of parturient *Rangifer* cows is often northward in latitude, or towards increasing elevations. This is thought to be an evolutionary response to temporal and spatial resource variation that will maximize calf survival, e.g., increase available forage quantity and quality, or reduce the risk of neonate predation (Bergerud & Page 1987, Fryxell *et al.* 1988, Klein 1990, Albon & Langvatn 1992, Griffith *et al.* 2002, Russell *et al.* 2002, Post *et al.* 2003, Loe *et al.* 2005). There is no doubt that calving areas are essential to productivity of a caribou population, and that access to these has direct consequences at the population level (Carroll *et al.* 2005).

Carroll *et al.* (2005) found that calving sites were primarily related to the timing and presence of snowmelt. Parturition and subsequent lactation represent enormous energy expenditures for cows (Boertje 1985, Bergerud *et al.* 2007), yet parturient caribou employ a capital reproductive strategy, i.e., nitrogen demands throughout gestation and early lactation are chiefly covered by maternal body reserves, which were deposited late in the previous growing season (Moen *et al.* 2006, Barboza & Parker 2008, Taillon *et al.* 2013). Thus, peak parturition can precede green-up by several weeks (Durant *et al.* 2005, Moen *et al.* 2006, Barboza & Parker 2008, Taillon *et al.* 2013), and in fact, parturient cows normally arrive at calving areas before green-up has occurred (Whitten & Cameron 1980, Kellyhouse 2001). Once green-up begins, calving

areas are associated with high rates of biomass increase (Kellyhouse 2001), and the emergent plants are high in soluble carbohydrates, nitrogen and phosphorus, which deteriorate as summer advances (White *et al.* 1975, Whitten & Cameron 1980, Jorgensen *et al.* 2002). Thus, emergent forage at calving sites may well coincide with the birthing cows' period of greatest energy needs, which is about three weeks post-calving (Parker *et al.* 1990).

As regards available forage quantity and quality at calving, rugged terrain, even in lowlands, widens the period of emergent forage availability in areas of patchy snowmelt (Nelleman & Thomsen 1994). Thus, high elevation would not be a prerequisite to emergent forage on the rough-featured AM region. AM lowlands can have patchy snowmelt with emergent vegetation underway, yet most parturient adult AM cows birthed at relatively high elevations of ca. 600 m or more. Given mean calving date, 30 May, and the ca. 65°N latitude of the Central region, emergent vegetation is unlikely at the elevations typically chosen for birthing by AM cows. AM calving appears to occur where food resources are limited and vegetation green-up many weeks in the waiting, e.g., maximum NDVI's (normalized difference vegetation index, 'density of green') across the Central region generally do not occur until July (Tøttrup 2009).

Why would AM cows choose high elevations or xeric areas? Why not birth in the snowmelt occurring in the Central region's lowlands? The latter would permit access to emergent forage, which as spring progressed could be pursued up the readily available elevation gradients throughout the region. Since insect harassment first begins several weeks post-calving, escape from these is not likely a factor in birthing site choice. Insect relief could, however, keep cows at high elevations, which are often windy, in the post-calving period. Decreasing the neonate predation risk is a mote point; because large predators have been absent in West Greenland since at least the 1870's (Vibe 1981). The elevations chosen by AM cows suggest the possibility of greater nutrient value contained in emergent vegetation associated with snowmelt in highlands, and that it is available over a longer period. Future investigation of the nutrient value and period length of emergent vegetation at high elevation versus lowlands may cast light on this conundrum.

Weather might also influence calving site choice. The Akia-Maniitsoq region is exposed to south westerly storm systems. Birthing cows choosing high elevations or dry xeric areas close to the Greenland Ice Cap may be reducing

the risk of unfavourable weather conditions for neonate survival, e.g., rain, which could increase neonate mortality through excessive heat loss associated with cold stress hypothermia. Heavy rainfall and wind can drastically increase neonate mortality in Arctic animal populations (Blix & Steen 1979, Mallory *et al.* 2009, Anctil *et al.* 2014, Yannic *et al.* 2014) including caribou neonates (Kelsall 1968, Blix 1980). Even without wind, wet neonate heat loss increases 5-fold (Lentz & Hart 1960, Hart *et al.* 1961, Markussen *et al.* 1985). Although rain coupled with wind increases neonate mortality, its role on parturient caribou migration and calving site choice has been ignored (Miller & Gunn 1986). Reducing the likelihood of exposing neonates to rain and wet substrates would benefit offspring survival in large ungulates (Azzam *et al.* 1993). This hypothesis that high elevation (combined with 65°N lat.) or xeric areas promotes neonate survival by reducing the risk of rain, needs further study. If true, this may clarify what options are open to parturient cows on ranges with low relief landscapes where the only rain avoidance choices may be locations of driest climate or the most northerly latitudes possible.

Interestingly, having a yearling-at-heel (calf from the previous spring) appeared to affect a cow's elevation choice (median 186 m lower) for parturition. The difference approached significance ($P = 0.058$, $df = 10$, $t = 2.2281$) and may be biologically significant. While cows are capital breeders, i.e., rely on body reserves for birthing and initial lactation, her yearling-at-heel may have fewer body reserves remaining at winter's end, making high elevations, snow-bound, with reduced forage availability less than ideal. Parturient cows with yearling-at-heel from the previous spring may choose birthing sites at lower elevations to balance their yearling's forage needs against enhancing survival of the coming neonate. To date, there are no studies addressing parturient caribou calving site choice in the presence or absence of a yearling-at-heel. Aerial observation of parturient cows pre-calving combined with investigations of pre- and post-calving relocations, might ascertain if this trade-off is occurring.

Management Implications

Mortality 2008-2010

Adult female and calf survival are the two key demographic factors that determine population growth rates (Hatter & Bergerud 1991). The 2008-2010 mortality among the AM satellite-collared cows was disturbingly high: 26 of

the 40 collared cows died over the two-year study period. This is 65% mortality. Over half the deaths may have been due to hunting. The season in which the assumed natural mortalities occurred, might indicate whether weather, nutrition or disease played a role in those deaths. Of the 11 assumed natural mortalities, over half were in June-July. This timing would seem to invalidate weather or nutrition as factors, and rather suggests the possibility of disease, e.g., from complications associated with birthing. Early winter accounted for four deaths and late winter one. Winter mortality can be linked to adverse environmental and nutritional factors. Regardless, too many died.

Caribou population declines are influenced by multiple factors, e.g., climate change, human causes, habitat, anthropogenic habitat loss or alteration, predation, parasites, insects, diseases, invasive species, competition, stochastic events and intraspecific competition (Vors & Boyce 2009, Festa-Bianchet *et al.* 2011, Joly & Klein 2011). Regardless of the cause, caribou population declines can result when these occasion a high cow mortality. The recent rapid decline in abundance of the Torngat Mountain caribou of Quebec-Labrador was caused by an annual adult cow mortality of 13% (Bélanger & Côté 2016). The 2008 and 2009 mortality among AM satellite-collared cows was 32% and 44% respectively. This is more than double that which caused the abrupt decline in Torngat Mountain caribou numbers. Caribou calf recruitment rates below 15% also result in population decline (Environment Canada 2011, Bergerud *et al.* 2007). In 2005 and 2010, AM late-winter calf recruitment rates were below that threshold. If the high mortality of collared cows reflected overall rates in the AM population combined with the known poor calf recruitment, then rapid population decline could be expected. In fact, the 2010 abundance survey documented greatly decreased abundance. From 2001 to 2010, AM caribou abundance declined by 50-70%.

Since adult female and calf survival are essential for recovery of caribou numbers, we recommend protecting and managing several seasonal habitats. Specifically, those that facilitate or enhance body condition and survival of adult females and calves, and therefore include calving: pre- & post-calving, mid/late summer, and mid- & late winter habitats. We recommend prohibiting winter hunting of the AM population, owing to the negative impacts of winter hunting on caribou abundance (Cuyler *et al.* 2016). Further, if future aerial surveys of AM caribou suggest further decline or failure to recover, then excluding all cows, and calves, from hunter harvest is one further option that could be considered.

Calving

Identifying caribou calving habitat and birth timing is prerequisite to implementing measures offsetting anticipated rapid anthropogenic change. Greenland conservation measures have used a 20 May to 20 June calving period and the assumption that exclusive inland calving grounds exist in proximity to the Greenland Ice Cap.

For AM cows, in the period 2008-2010, calving began earlier than previously accepted. We also documented dispersed spacing-away at calving in a continuum across the entire region at significantly higher elevations than any other activity period. Peak calving habitat attributes constituted approx. 42% of the region, while for the entire calving period this became approx. 45%. Our results support Cuyler & Linnell (2004) and negate the assumption that AM calving is only close to the Greenland Ice Cap and aggregated at a distinct exclusive calving ground.

The apparent lack of aggregations and dispersed distribution of AM caribou cows at calving suggests the need for calving habitat conservation approaches unique to Greenland. Currently, habitat fitting the criteria for observed calving sites is relatively available and widespread rather than limited to small exclusive areas. This new knowledge is valuable for fresh management strategies aimed at conserving AM caribou, specifically in the face of possible rapid anthropogenic disturbance and development. In the past, only an exclusive sub-area of the total AM region was protected during calving. However, the desired beneficial effect(s) of conservation and protection measures for calving might best be attained if effort is directed at shifting forward the time period for protection measures and recognizing the need for broad scale habitat management (using the habitat criteria) across the region. High elevations with a southerly aspect and persistent snow cover from the past winter as well as xeric areas close to the Ice Cap embody AM calving site habitat. Further, although this habitat type is currently widely available, high cow fidelity to previously used birthing sites and a warming Arctic may necessitate protection of vulnerable and possibly ever dwindling habitat suitable for calving in the AM region. Further work is required to refine habitat selection and inter-annual variability beyond this two-year study.

Disturbance

Both wild caribou and semi-domestic reindeer (*R. t. tarandus*) respond to anthropogenic disturbance by changing their movements and distribution (Bergerud 1974, Whitten & Cameron 1983, Vistnes & Nellemann 2008). Avoidance is to at least 4 km of human development (Nellemann *et al.* 2003). The degree of avoidance is positively correlated to the level of human activity (Smith & Cameron 1983, Dyer *et al.* 2001). Sensitivity was greatest among parturient cows and cows with calves (Dau & Cameron 1986, Cameron *et al.* 1992; 2005, Nelleman & Cameron 1996, Vistnes & Nellemann 2001, Weir *et al.* 2007). In another ungulate, human disturbance has significant impact on calving site selection, even overriding environmental factors (Singh *et al.* 2010). There is a correlation between increasing anthropogenic change and decreasing caribou calf recruitment (Nellemann *et al.* 2003, Cameron *et al.* 2005), and Festa-Bianchet *et al.* (2011) observed that cows displaced from preferred calving areas had reduced calf productivity and survival. Denying cows access to calving areas has direct negative effects at the population level (Carroll *et al.* 2005).

If mitigation of human disturbance comes under management consideration, then one example of an area that received high probability of cow occurrence in all seasonal activity periods was the Narssarssuaq Valley, which runs northeast from Qugsuk Bay on the north side of the inner Godthåbsfjord. This small area is clearly important for the caribou year round.

As regards winter range, caribou need large continuous blocks without fragmentation (Daniels 2016). Anthropogenic landscape change is a recognized factor in caribou population declines (Hornseth & Rempel 2016, Hunt *et al.* 2016, Kansas *et al.* 2016, MacNeary *et al.* 2016, Ronson 2016,). Increased disturbance of caribou in winter can result in increased energy use for caribou and may also drive them to shift range use (Bradshaw *et al.* 1997, Aastrup 2004). Specifically, recreational skidoo / snow sledge use can displace caribou from optimal winter ranges (Grant *et al.* 2016). Currently, for caribou conservation in North America, risk-based management threshold of 65% completely undisturbed habitat is being applied to caribou range (Johnson *et al.* 2016). In Greenland, disturbance thresholds have yet to be considered.

Landscape use

Conservation and management actions for highly mobile species occupying large annual and cumulative ranges should reflect their ecology and be implemented at large landscape scales (Hanski 1998). It has been said that, “*Caribou need room-to-roam*”. They depend upon large undisturbed intact landscapes and migration corridors. While human impact on mammal migrations can be high and lie behind population declines (Harris *et al.* 2009), among ungulates, rapid population collapse can follow disruption of migratory corridors (Bolger *et al.* 2008). Effective proactive management and conservation of undisturbed intact landscapes and migration corridors would foster caribou conservation.

Calving grounds are commonly considered the ultimate critical area used by caribou annually and needing protection (Committee 1993). Caribou cannot thrive, however, if all protection/conservation efforts are directed only at calving habitat. Aastrup (2004) recognized that it was not only calving range that was essential for caribou. Caribou depend on access to all seasonal habitats. If less essential range became for example inaccessible, overgrazing of another essential seasonal range might occur. While some ranges, like calving, may seem most important, all seasonal ranges are vital and must not be neglected or ignored. Knowledge of the areas used by caribou during all ecological periods is basic for habitat management and conservation. If protections apply only to calving cows and their calving habitat, then recovery or sustainability of caribou populations are not guaranteed.

During the summer and fall pre-rut periods caribou regain body condition before breeding (Russell Martel & Nixon 1993). To this end, insect relief habitat plays a primary role (Wilson *et al.* 2012). In summer, caribou seek windy locations and snow patches for insect relief (Joly & Klein 2011). The reduced movement spent avoiding insect harassment translates into more time for foraging (Mörschel & Klein 1997). Increased movements caused by insect harassment are linked to poor calf growth over summer and low autumn weights (Weladjji *et al.* 2003, Couturier *et al.* 2009). Since insect relief habitat is vital to caribou energetics (Weladjji *et al.* 2003, Hughes *et al.* 2009), conservation measures are necessary regarding human development on those habitats (Wilson *et al.* 2012).

Late summer habitat is also essential. Capital breeders, which include caribou cows, deposit their body reserves late in the previous growing season and

then use these reserves to compensate for inadequate food availability in early reproduction (Moen *et al.* 2006, Barboza & Parker 2008, Taillon *et al.* 2013). The summer and pre-rut periods also determine cow body condition during the breeding period, which affects the timing and synchrony of calving and calf survival the following spring (Russell *et al.* 1993, Gerhart 1995, Whitten 1995). Also, winter is an important period for caribou survival, and many migrate to habitat where food quality and availability affect activity budgets (Russell *et al.* 1993). Further, although late summer, fall and winter ranges underpin reproduction and survival, these are limited in area for AM caribou. Conservation efforts for AM caribou could include preserving caribou access to those late summer, fall and winter ranges, minimizing and mitigating anthropogenic disturbance (e.g., prohibit use of skidoo/snow sledges), and use autumn hunter harvest to keep densities of AM caribou below the recommended, 1.2/km², for the scarce winter range.

Although AM calving habitat is essential, policy makers need to recognize the value of other seasonal ranges and ensure connectivity is maintained among these ranges. Further, caribou shift their seasonal range use over time and such shifts may be common and should be anticipated by management (Gunn *et al.* 2008, Nagy & Campbell 2012, Taillon *et al.* 2012). Thus, we recommend that suitable Central region ranges, currently unused (at least by the satellite-collared cows), be managed and protected for potential future use by caribou. We recommend that when and if large (65% of total home range (Johnson *et al.* 2016)) protected tracts of undisturbed habitat are under consideration, that these must include a variety of components that are relevant for several caribou activities including foraging, calving, and insect relief and provide connectivity [movement corridors] among preferred habitats.

Recommendations for future satellite collaring studies

We recommend a satellite-collar deployment period of 4-5 consecutive years, while simultaneously maintaining a minimum of 20 collared-cows annually per population, i.e., re-furbish and re-deploy collars when animals die. Other options would include 10 collared-cows over a 10-year period, or similar variations. This would provide sufficient data for robust analyses and conclusions, e.g., on seasonal habitat fidelity and population sub-structuring. As regards the latter, genetics studies, within and among the caribou populations [regions] of West Greenland, could provide additional information on the degree of genetic exchange within and between regions.

Effective caribou management in Greenland would benefit from satellite collar studies in all the major populations, i.e., Kangerlussuaq-Sisimiut, Akia-Maniitsoq, Ameralik and Qeqertarsuatsiaat. These vary in, among other things, latitudinal gradient, forage, topography, presence/absence of rain-shadows and genetics. Their combined study would improve understanding and possibly permit predictions for the various smaller populations in Greenland. Knowledge gained would also support management decisions about which infrastructure and develop plans would least disrupt specific caribou habitats (Wilson 2012).

Since caribou/reindeer generally demonstrate a high degree of sexual segregation (Cameron & Whitten 1979, Jakimchuk *et al.* 1987, Skogland 1989), we recommend including males to investigate divergent seasonal habitat use by sex. We currently have no data on the movement and activity behaviour of the male segment of the population.

Owing to logistics, the current study collared parturient cows in early May. We assume this was poor timing because birthing was only a few weeks away. Subsequently, seven (18%) cows deemed parturient at capture and collaring, appeared to lose their calves. If true, then it is likely that the stress of capture and collaring contributed. To avoid this possibility, we recommend setting the collar specifications and actually receiving delivery of these well in advance of the aerial collaring itself. Collar delivery should be in summer or early autumn. Collar deployment could occur in late autumn or early winter, when mature males lack antlers and cows are many months from parturition.

We recommend that budgets for satellite collaring studies include at least the following important actions, 1) collar retrieval, refurbishment and redeployment, 2) relocations of collared cows, and 3) information campaigns for the public. Retrieval of satellite-collars from cows that died, in addition to re-deployment of a working collar, would permit an evaluation as to the cause of mortality. Relocations of satellite-collared cows serve several essential purposes and are necessary. Checking for a calf-at-heel following a daily movement pattern indicating that a birthing event took place would confirm parturition and calving site. Checking for continued presence of their calf-at-heel, at both 8 and 11 months, would provide needed calf survival data important for predicting future population trends. Finally, the public must be informed about the protected status of satellite-collared cows, possible

penalties for illegal harvest and the financial resources wasted when a collared cow is removed untimely from telemetry studies. Hunter harvest exacerbated collared-cow mortality in the current study. An information campaign could increase public understanding of the significance of collar data for effective management of habitat and caribou to the benefit of all.

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Appendix 1

Capture of Akia-Maniitsoq caribou cows, 1-7 May 2008.

Figure 14. Satellite collar deployment locations, 40 caribou cows, 1-7 May 2008. Red and orange mark the 20 Vectronics Iridium satellite GPS collars; the 10 SirTrack release mechanism are red, and the 10 Lotek release mechanism are orange. Blue marks the 20 Telonics ARGOS GPS collars. Fuel depot is marked by black gas tank. (1 May – Red/Orange circles; 2 May – Red/Orange top heavy triangles; 4 May – Red/Orange bottom heavy triangles; 5 May – Red/Orange squares; 6 May – Blue squares; 7 May – Blue circles).

Table 16. Satellite collar deployment positions on 40 caribou cows, 1-7 May 2008, West Greenland Iridium collars, by Vectronics, had release mechanisms made by SirTrack (ST) and Lotek (L). Telonics produced the ARGOS collars and release mechanisms for these.

Capture & Deployment position		Date	Cow	Collar	PTT
NORTH	WEST	2008	Pregnant	Type	ID
64° 53' 38.0"	50° 56' 41.7"	01 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5711
64° 53' 59.7"	50° 56' 53.6"	01 May	Yes	Iridium L	5722
64° 55' 01.9"	51° 16' 25.1"	01 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5712
64° 57' 55.3"	51° 13' 52.5"	01 May	Yes	Iridium L	5715
64° 48' 23.9"	51° 22' 54.9"	01 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5705
64° 44' 05.4"	51° 33' 02.9"	01 May	Yes	Iridium L	5723
64° 43' 20.6"	51° 43' 07.9"	01 May	Yes	Iridium L	5724
64° 49' 12.8"	50° 15' 18.3"	02 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5706
64° 58' 52.8"	50° 09' 50.5"	02 May	No	Iridium L	5720
65° 01' 08.9"	50° 12' 49.2"	02 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5713
65° 06' 42.8"	50° 22' 44.5"	02 May	Yes	Iridium L	5721
65° 03' 13.2"	51° 02' 34.5"	02 May	No	Iridium ST	5710
65° 15' 33.0"	51° 05' 02.7"	02 May	Yes	Iridium L	5717
65° 36' 58.4"	51° 58' 16.6"	04 May	No	Iridium L	5719
65° 39' 24.2"	51° 23' 38.1"	04 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5709
65° 39' 26.6"	51° 21' 18.5"	04 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5707
65° 39' 46.8"	51° 20' 29.3"	04 May	Yes	Iridium L	5716
65° 14' 07.2"	50° 48' 10.8"	05 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5714
65° 15' 08.2"	50° 44' 02.9"	05 May	Yes	Iridium L	5718
65° 27' 30.0"	50° 28' 46.9"	05 May	Yes	Iridium ST	5708
64° 42' 08.0"	51° 33' 06.9"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	615884
64° 42' 58.7"	51° 33' 04.8"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	613848
64° 44' 29.1"	51° 45' 56.2"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	613824
64° 45' 14.9"	51° 43' 21.9"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	613820
64° 53' 18.8"	51° 22' 43.4"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	614477
64° 50' 12.1"	50° 56' 21.4"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	613823
64° 49' 00.0"	50° 55' 51.8"	06 May	Yes	ARGOS	614480
65° 04' 58.6"	51° 38' 22.4"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	614457
65° 08' 03.7"	51° 43' 36.8"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	615882
65° 16' 11.0"	51° 32' 59.6"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613836
65° 19' 30.0"	51° 34' 23.9"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	614453
65° 21' 46.1"	51° 28' 52.7"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	615881
65° 25' 54.3"	51° 25' 37.2"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613847
65° 25' 50.6"	51° 22' 16.7"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613838
65° 29' 06.8"	51° 16' 43.8"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613846
65° 34' 28.6"	51° 56' 08.1"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613851
65° 06' 18.5"	50° 45' 55.9"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613833
65° 11' 37.2"	50° 25' 47.1"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613856
65° 10' 07.8"	50° 25' 41.9"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	614481
65° 09' 43.4"	50° 26' 07.7"	07 May	Yes	ARGOS	613850

Figure 15. Caribou movement routes observed, 1-7 May 2008, for the Akia-Maniitsoq population in the Central Region. Movement was generally from southwest to northeast throughout the region. Arrows indicate heavy trails or large numbers of animals seen moving. Many areas were not flown over, which makes further routes possible.

Appendix 2

SBIC (Schwarz-Bayesian information criterion) differences for the 10 best-fit resource selection models for each activity period

Table 17. Calving caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit calving activity period resource selection models	SBIC	Δ SBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on Δ SBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-150298.7	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-150286.8	12	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-150236.2	63	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-150227.6	71	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-150223.4	75	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-150206.8	92	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-150196.3	102	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-150181	118	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-150179.7	119	Very strong
open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-150161	138	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 18. Peak-calving caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit peak-calving activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137189.4	0	Best-fit model
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137186.9	3	Positive
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137175.6	14	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137172.6	17	Very strong
elevation + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137159.6	30	Very strong
elevation + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137140.7	49	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-137118.7	71	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-137109.3	80	Very strong
open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137104.9	85	Very strong
copse + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137104.6	85	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 19. Post-calving caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit post-calving activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-136853.8	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-136842.2	12	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-136783.2	71	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-136780.9	73	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-136779.9	74	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-136778.0	76	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-136775.6	78	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-136770.6	83	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-136768.5	85	Very strong
elevation + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-136766.0	88	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 20. Early summer caribou resource selection models

			Relative preference for best-fit model based on Δ SBIC*
Ten best-fit early summer activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140048.1	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-140036.7	11	Very strong
elevation + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140012.2	36	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140005.7	42	Very strong
elevation + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-140000.1	48	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-139994.3	54	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-139992.6	56	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-139992.2	56	Very strong
copse + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-139987.6	61	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-139985.1	63	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 21. Mid/late summer caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit mid/late summer activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140439.1	0	Best-fit model
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140410.6	29	Very strong
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse	-140408.5	31	Very strong
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-140406.6	33	Very strong
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse + fen + grass	-140406.2	33	Very strong
heath + open + heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-140402.4	37	Very strong
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse + fen	-140401.9	37	Very strong
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-140398.6	41	Very strong
elevation + heath + open + heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-140398.0	41	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass	-140391.4	48	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 22. Fall/pre-breeding caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit fall/pre-breeding activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137204.7	0	Best-fit model
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137198.2	7	Strong
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137196.2	9	Strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137190.5	14	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137188.8	16	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass	-137188.4	16	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass	-137187.4	17	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-137184.4	20	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-137183.2	22	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137180.9	24	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 23. Breeding (rut) caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit breeding activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-143218.3	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-143213.1	5	Positive
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-143126.4	92	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-143118.2	100	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-143117.2	101	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-143111.7	107	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass	-143093.9	124	Very strong
heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-143043.9	174	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-143034.5	184	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-143034.0	184	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 24. Post-breeding /late fall caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit post-breeding/late fall activity period resource selection models	SBIC	Δ SBIC	Relative preference for
			best-fit model based on Δ SBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-154203.3	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-154196.2	7	Strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-154135.9	67	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-154128.7	75	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-154081.3	122	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-154079.6	124	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass	-154048.3	155	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen	-153983.9	219	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse	-153957.5	246	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-153946.3	257	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 25. Early/mid-winter activity period caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit early/mid-winter activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-144092.0	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-144085.8	6	Positive
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-144036.5	56	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-144031.9	60	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-144021.2	71	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-143994.7	97	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass	-143983.1	109	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse	-143973.9	118	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen	-143971.0	121	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-143962.3	130	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 26. Late winter activity period caribou resource selection models

Ten best-fit late winter activity period resource selection models	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-139452.9	0	Best-fit model
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-139451.2	2	Weak
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-139417.2	36	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-139413.4	40	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-139411.0	42	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed	-139402.4	51	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass	-139387.0	66	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen	-139377.5	75	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse	-139370.1	83	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-139345.7	107	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Table 27. Pre-calving activity period caribou resource selection models

	SBIC	ΔSBIC	Relative preference for best-fit model based on ΔSBIC*
Ten best-fit pre-calving activity period resource selection models			
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137443.7	0	Best-fit model
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water	-137442.2	2	Weak
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137440.7	3	Positive
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137439.6	4	Positive
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-137431.4	12	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-137425.4	18	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock	-137424.8	19	Very strong
elevation + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment	-137418.6	25	Very strong
elevation + heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed	-137406.5	37	Very strong
heath + open-heath + copse + fen + grass + snow-bed + wind-exposed + soil/rock + sediment + water + snow/ice	-137406.3	37	Very strong

*Relative preference for best-fit model based on Hardin & Hilbe (2012).

Appendix 3

Habitat selection by Greenland caribou (Rangifer tarandus groenlandicus) during the CALVING period relative to those selected during the other activity periods, based on latent selection difference (LSD) function model comparisons, 2008-2010.

Table 28. Calving VERSUS post-calving, early summer, and mid /late summer activity periods

Habitat types	Calving versus post-calving				Calving versus early summer				Calving versus mid /late summer			
	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS*	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS
heath	-0.301	0.094	0.001	26	0.029	0.084	0.732	=	-0.661	0.094	0.000	48
openheath	0.520	0.098	0.000	>100	0.858	0.084	0.000	>100	0.478	0.085	0.000	>100
copse	0.059	0.103	0.567	=	0.112	0.094	0.233	=	-0.004	0.085	0.964	=
fen	-0.130	0.100	0.192	=	-0.200	0.087	0.022	18	-0.093	0.090	0.302	=
grass	0.120	0.076	0.113	=	0.145	0.070	0.039	>100	0.134	0.071	0.059	=
snowbed	-0.366	0.170	0.032	31	-0.429	0.143	0.003	=	-0.488	0.141	0.001	39
windexp	-0.003	0.097	0.974	=	0.378	0.087	0.000	>100	0.842	0.085	0.000	>100
soilrock	0.042	0.084	0.616	=	-0.102	0.077	0.188	=	-0.355	0.081	0.000	30
sediment	-0.170	0.121	0.158	=	-0.372	0.099	0.000	31	-0.328	0.103	0.001	28
water	0.310	0.139	0.026	>100	0.065	0.115	0.572	=	-0.092	0.116	0.428	=
snowice	0.889	0.784	0.257	=	0.297	0.466	0.524	=	-	-	-	-
_cons	0.700	0.133	0.000		-0.230	0.117	0.050		0.483	0.121	0.000	

*Relative selection (RS) was calculated for variables with coefficients significantly different from 0 as $\exp(b)$ when $b > 0$ and as $[1 - \exp(b)]$ when $b < 0$ (Latham, Latham & Boyce, 2011b). Relative selection values < 100 indicate that use of the habitat during calving was significantly less by x% than that for the season being compared, values > 100 indicate use of habitat during calving was significantly greater than that for the season being compared, and = indicates habitat use during calving and season being compared were not significantly different.

Table 29. Calving VERSUS fall /pre-breeding, breeding, and post-breeding/late fall activity periods

use	Calving versus fall /pre-breeding				Calving versus breeding				Calving versus post-breeding/late fall			
	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS*	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS
heath	-0.712	0.104	0.000	51	-1.134	0.104	0.000	68	-1.339	0.092	0.000	74
openheath	0.210	0.098	0.033	>100	0.217	0.086	0.012	>100	-0.139	0.081	0.086	=
copse	0.042	0.093	0.650	=	0.094	0.079	0.233	=	0.140	0.069	0.043	>100
fen	0.061	0.107	0.566	=	-0.161	0.093	0.082	=	-0.339	0.078	0.000	29
grass	-0.229	0.076	0.002	20	-0.187	0.069	0.007	17	0.098	0.063	0.121	=
snowbed	-0.135	0.181	0.456	=	0.083	0.168	0.624	=	0.143	0.150	0.340	=
windexp	0.672	0.092	0.000	>100	1.224	0.082	0.000	>100	1.126	0.071	0.000	>100
soilrock	-0.021	0.086	0.805	=	-0.135	0.082	0.099	=	0.314	0.073	0.000	>100
sediment	-0.043	0.129	0.738	=	-0.554	0.113	0.000	43	-0.612	0.100	0.000	46
water	-0.093	0.141	0.511	=	0.516	0.132	0.000	>100	0.353	0.112	0.002	>100
snowice	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.858	0.801	0.284	=
_cons	1.054	0.137	0.000		0.767	0.127	0.000		0.614	0.117	0.000	

*Relative selection (RS) was calculated for variables with coefficients significantly different from 0 as $\exp(b)$ when $b > 0$ and as $[1 - \exp(b)]$ when $b < 0$ (Latham, Latham & Boyce, 2011b). Relative selection values < 100 indicate that use of the habitat during calving was significantly less by x% than that for the season being compared, values > 100 indicate use of habitat during calving was significantly greater than that for the season being compared, and = indicates habitat use during calving and season being compared were not significantly different.

Table 30. Calving VERSUS early/mid-winter, late-winter, and pre-calving activity periods

use	Calving versus early/mid-winter				Calving versus late-winter				Calving versus pre-calving			
	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS*	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS	Coefficient	S.E.	P-value	RS
heath	-0.996	0.088	0.000	63	-0.963	0.101	0.000	62	-0.134	0.090	0.135	=
openheath	-0.355	0.092	0.000	30	0.069	0.095	0.470	=	0.075	0.100	0.455	=
copse	0.101	0.076	0.187	=	0.060	0.086	0.488	=	0.250	0.096	0.009	>100
fen	-0.429	0.079	0.000	35	-0.189	0.091	0.037	17	-0.274	0.092	0.003	24
grass	0.336	0.066	0.000	>100	0.281	0.074	0.000	>100	0.165	0.074	0.027	>100
snowbed	-0.138	0.149	0.353	=	0.175	0.170	0.303	=	0.131	0.165	0.428	=
windexp	0.482	0.076	0.000	>100	0.445	0.085	0.000	>100	0.278	0.090	0.002	>100
soilrock	0.164	0.073	0.026	>100	0.078	0.083	0.348	=	0.321	0.082	0.000	>100
sediment	-0.643	0.101	0.000	47	-0.886	0.107	0.000	59	-0.675	0.113	0.000	49
water	0.429	0.115	0.000	>100	0.271	0.125	0.030	>100	0.048	0.125	0.698	=
snowice	0.740	0.795	0.352	=	-0.965	0.427	0.024	62	0.612	0.669	0.360	=
_cons	1.125	0.121	0.000		1.142	0.131	0.000		0.624	0.128	0.000	

*Relative selection (RS) was calculated for variables with coefficients significantly different from 0 as $\exp(b)$ when $b > 0$ and as $[1 - \exp(b)]$ when $b < 0$ (Latham, Latham & Boyce, 2011b). Relative selection values < 100 indicate that use of the habitat during calving was significantly less by x% than that for the season being compared, values > 100 indicate use of habitat during calving was significantly greater than that for the season being compared, and = indicates habitat use during calving and season being compared were not significantly different.

Appendix 4

Reproductive status collared cows alive at calving

Table 31. Reproductive status of collared cows, assumed given clear daily movement pattern. 'Unknown' were unclear daily movement pattern, indicating did not calf or calf dead / died.

Collar ID	2008	2009	2010
5705	Calved	Did NOT calf	
5706	Calved		
5707	Calved		
5708	Calved	Did NOT calf	
5709	Calved		
5710	Did NOT calf	Did NOT calf	
5711	Calved	Calved	
5712	Calved	Calved	
5713	Calved		
5714	Calved	Did NOT calf	Calved
5715	Calved		
5716	Calved		
5717	Calved		
5718	Calved		
5719	Did NOT calf	Calved	
5720	Calved	Calved	
5721	Calved		
5722	Calved	Did NOT calf	
5723	Calved	Did NOT calf	
5724	Calved	Calved	
613820	Calved		
613823	Calved	unknown	
613824	Calved	unknown	
613833	unknown		
613836	Calved	Calved	unknown
613838	Calved		
613846	Calved		
613847	Calved	Calved	unknown
613848	unknown	Calved	Calved
613850	unknown	Calved	Calved
613851	unknown	Calved	Calved
613856	unknown	Calved	Calved
614453	Calved	unknown	
614457	Calved	Calved	
614477	unknown		
614480	Calved	unknown	Did NOT calf
614481	Calved	Calved	Calved
615881	Calved	unknown	
615882	Calved	Calved	Calved
615884	unknown		

Appendix 5

Equipment recommendations for satellite collaring

- 1) The teardrop form of the Vectronics collars might be changed to an oval 'circle' form, which is better suited to bear battery and sender, and sit properly on the animal's neck.

- 2) Check the current state of data derived from Iridium versus Argos satellites. In the period 2008-2010 it appeared that the daily movement patterns were clearer from the Iridium satellite data.

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